

The Coptic Clerks in Egypt through Study of Rare Documents of Barclays Bank in 20th Century

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Abstract

The research sheds light on the role and status of the Coptic clerks in the after Muhammad Ali Pasha period, and their related to the money exchange function, financial transactions since the tenth century AD until the twentieth century. Through of study of twenty one documents varying related to Barclays Bank - Egypt, written in the English and Arabic language, such as official letters, claims and a broadcast receiver license. Back its importance due to sheds light on the economic and political conditions in Egypt from the beginning of the Second World War to its end, and role the Banks in Egypt for affecting about economic conditions. The research also presented the most famous Coptic clerks working at Barclays Bank at the time, and the extent of their social state and their position. The research also touched on the raw materials used in various types of correspondence, including papers, inks, and pens of all kinds, and the most famous companies that manufactured paper and inks.

Keywords

Documents; Barclays Bank; Broadcast Receiver License; Coptic Clerks; Water Mark; Ink; Official Letters; Memorandum.

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الكتبة الأقباط في مصر من خلال دراسة مجموعة من الوثائق النادرة لبنك باركليز خلال القرن العشرين

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الملخص

يسلط البحث الضوء على دور ومكانة الكتبة الأقباط في فترة ما بعد محمد علي باشا، وارتباطهم بوظيفة الصرافة، والمعاملات المالية منذ القرن العاشر الميلادي حتى القرن العشرين. من خلال دراسة واحد وعشرين وثيقة مختلفة خاصة لبنك باركليز - مصر، مكتوبة باللغتين الإنجليزية والعربية، مثل الخطابات الرسمية والمطالبات و رخصة استقبال البث. وترجع أهميته إلى إلقاء الضوء على الأوضاع الاقتصادية والسياسية في مصر منذ بداية الحرب العالمية الثانية وحتى نهايتها، ودور البنوك في مصر في التأثير على الأوضاع الاقتصادية. كما عرض البحث أشهر الموظفين الأقباط العاملين لبنك باركليز في ذلك الوقت، ومدى حالتهم الاجتماعية ومكانتهم. كما تطرق البحث إلى المواد الخام المستخدمة في المراسلات بأنواعها المختلفة، من الأوراق والأحبار والأقلام بأنواعها، وأشهر الشركات التي قامت بتصنيع الورق والأحبار.

الكلمات الدالة

وثائق؛ بنك باركليز؛ رخصة استقبال البث؛ الكتبة الأقباط؛ علامات مائية؛ حبر؛ خطابات رسمية.

1. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

The story starts since, that Egypt had a body of government employees whose history extends back thousands of years, and its traditions that it preserved and pass on from one generation to another. Bookkeeping and accounting have been related with Jews throughout the centuries, and tax collectors, lands surveyors and money changers to the Copts since the tenth century AD.¹

Al-Qalqashandi tells us about the nicknames of the Coptic scribes (clerks) attribute to their names, and he says: "And they have nicknames that belong to them, so they say in 'Abdullah' 'Shams al-Din,' and in 'Abd al-Raziq' 'Taj al-Din' or 'Saad al-Din,' and in Ibrahim 'Alam al-Din', and in 'Majid' 'Majid al-Din', and in 'Wahba' 'Taqi al-Din' and so on."²

And he continues, saying: "They used nicknames, which were titled on them, most of which are start of the surname 'Alsheikh', and some of them follow the first drawing in the nickname in addition to the word of 'Al dawla' (the state), so he is called 'Wali al-Dawla' the (ruler of the state), and 'Sheikh Al-Muwaffaq.'" If one of them converted to Islam, the Alif and ALLam were dropped and the surname was added to the word "Al Din" (in place of "Sheikh"), so it is said in "Sheikh Shamsi" "Shams al-Din" and in "Sheikh Al Sfi" said "Sfi al-Din" and in "Wali al-Dawla" "Wali al-Din" and the like. And perhaps the nickname "Al dhimmi" (the Coptic clerk) does not agree with anything that is added to the nickname "Al Din" among the nicknames of Muslims, so if he embraces Islam, he should be given the closest nickname to him, such as "Al Sheikh Al Said" (the happy Sheikh), if he embraced Islam His nickname is "Saad al-Din", and so on.³

The job of clerks in government offices required basic conditions to access it, which are proficiency in reading, writing, arithmetic, and knowledge of the Turkish language. The head of office was called "the first clerk" in Arabic language or "Bash of clerk" in Turkish language, sometimes called "El Maelm", which means the teacher, usually was appointed the Copts in jobs of clerks. Some of them reach the position of "the first clerk".⁴

The French campaign within the late 18 AD and early 19 AD century exposed Egypt to a cultural shock through an encounter with the West. After the Ottoman empire restored its sovereignty, Mohamed Ali (1805–1849), motivated by his personal and military ambitions, launched into a significant program to modernize and development Egypt, in order to keep pace with the great development in Europe.

He shifted agriculture in Egypt from basin irrigation by the Nile flood to perennial irrigation, developed shipping transport by building the port of Alexandria, and dig the Mahmudiya canal. Mohamad Ali also started establishing an impressive industrial infrastructure. In 1840 because of a coalition headed by the British, he Militarily defeated, so was his dreams were thwarted and his development program was stopted.

In 1860s through American Civil War , cotton prices reached to high levels, thus attracting many foreign investors and also the men of the aristocracy to Egypt. So, Egypt became a major producer of cotton to textile industries and exports it. Within the reign of Ismael Pasha (1863–79), as an enlightened ruler, the opening of the Suez Canal some years later integrated Egypt's position as a middle center of shipping transport. Ismael Pasha hoped to form Egypt a part of Europe. The judiciary systems modernized with the promulgation of a civil law and therefore the establishment of civil courts. An elected assembly, with limited power, was called for. However, financial mismanagement and

¹ Shalaby 1989:11. For more about learning Coptic scribes and their children looks, Naseem 1983: 45- 46.

² Al-Qalqashandi 1915: 490.

³ Al-Qalqashandi 1915: 491.

⁴ Ramzy 1911: 80.

contest between France and England to control the Suez Canal motivated the British to take up the country. The second experiment to modernization was thus failed too, following a financial recession and a foreign control and occupation.¹

After the First World War, the British government conceded limited independence to Egypt (1922) result to the pressure of popular unrest that is beginning a nascent liberal state emerged. A liberal constitution was adopted (1923). Though the concept of economic development wasn't yet invented, the establishment of Banque Misr ignited national aspirations for economic independence alongside with the claim for political independence. The world economic crisis (the globe depression) of the 1930s took the most effective a part of the subsequent decade. With the Second World War, Egypt, like other British colonies, became a part of the war effort and joined the sterling block. With the end of the war, a chapter of recent Egypt was closed and a new era started with a military revolution and public in (1952).

Due to revolution of (1952) Egypt was well positioned to begin a new phase of development and the industrial revolution where establishment of spinning and weaving factories that depended on the production of Egyptian cotton². At midcentury, Egypt was better equipped than most developing countries.³

We conclude from this study that there are many reasons that encouraged Barclays Bank to invest its money and to take a position in Egypt:

- 1- Egypt's encouraging economic and investment climate.
- 2- Egypt was still under the guardianship of England.
- 3- Barclays Bank was one of the institutions that supply the British colonies.
- 4- Egyptian cotton is a vital and an important attraction factor; it is a profitable and secure trade.

II. GARMENT OR CLOTHES OF SCRIBES

The scribes in Egypt during the 19th and 20th centuries did not have his own uniform like the soldiers who were distinguished by special costumes, but their clothes were like the clothes of the Egyptian people, and according to their position, classes and job status, their clothes differed. Some of them were a simple and poor clerk with a low job status, and his clothes were simple, and some of them were of a high job position, so their expensive clothes resembled the clothes of princes at that time.

The scientists of the French campaign left us three drawings of three Coptic persons, whose drawings largely illustrate the form of the clothes of these Coptic scribes (clerk staff), although their drawings are small, but it suffices. It gives us a concept of form of its clothes, who were working for the state during the 19th and 20th centuries.⁴

From the study of their images, it was found that their clothes consisted of a long shirt (robes) or "jilbab", with a "belt" in the middle, topped by a long cloak open in the front completely with wide and long sleeves, and it was known as "kula" in the Ottoman era, while was worn from the bottom, wide trousers or pants Loose, tight from the foot.

This is in addition to the turbans of the head, which took various forms, each of which indicates the social and functional status of its owner. The prince was distinguished by a certain turban and bore a special form according to his function. Likewise, the scribe used his turban indicative of his position and job status during the 19th century.

¹ El Beblawi 2008: 3.

² Hawash 2007: 2.

³ El Beblawi 2008: 3.

⁴ Scientists of the French Campaign 2005, plate K, fig. 28.

These clothes developed after that, and the cloak became called the "Jubbah"¹ which was distinguished by the Azharites in the late 19th century. As for the "jilbab" or "robes", it became called the "kaftan",² and it was worn under the "Jubbah", but at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the form of the clothes changed completely, especially with the entry of the British into Egypt in 1886 AD, so the "cloak" changed to the "jacket". The "long robes" were changed to a "shirt", the "pants Loose" were changed to trousers, and the "turban" was changed to the "fez" or "Tarboosh". This became the form of the "scribe", who is called after that "El-Effendy" in Egypt, especially during the 20th century.

III. PROGRESS STYLE OF LEARN COPTIC SCRIBES

Since the 19th century, the methods of education for Coptic scribe have begun to change with the change in the new political situation of the state, the change in economic situation also, and with the modernity initiated by Muhammad Ali Pasha. Therefore, the Coptic scribe had to learn everything new in order to keep pace with the conditions of the times, and to ensure a prestigious job and a good social position.

This development went through four stages as follows:

3.1. The first stage starts from 1800 to 1863: During that period, the learning system within the "Al-Kotab" was the dominant system, and it was an old prevalent system in Egypt, which continued until the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, among Copts or Muslims. "El-moalem" he was a person responsible for teaching in it. He teaches the children elementary knowledge of reading, writing, and arithmetic, chapters of the Bible, melodies and psalms. But it is a rigid system that does not lead to development. Depends on indoctrination and memorization, and the teachers' wages were in kind.³

In the middle of that period, Muhammad Ali Pasha began establishing Amiri (governmental) schools serving the state, with the various disciplines needed by the modern state. Alongside it was Coptic schools for boys, and Coptic schools for girls, founded by Pope Cyril IV (110), nicknamed "The Father of Reform" in arabic "Abu Islah".⁴

3.2. The second stage, from 1863 to 1924: During that stage, Amiri (governmental) and private schools, Protestant and Catholic missionary schools. This is in addition to the establishment of the "National University" on 12/12/1908, and Ahmed Lutfi Al-Sayyid was appointed as its first director, and during the reign of Khedive Abbas Helmy II it was called (the Egyptian University), then called During the reign of Fouad I (Fouad I University), and after the 1952 revolution it was called (Cairo University).⁵

Among the most famous Coptic scribe (clerk) at that stage was "Iskandar Effendi Cosman," the nephew of Pope Kyrillos IV, "father of reform". Iskandar and his two brothers entered the Great Coptic School founded by Pope Kyrillos IV. Iskandar graduated while he was a poet and was fluent in Arabic, English, French and Coptic, and excelled in all of them. He worked until the year 1893 as a teacher at the American School, then resigned and worked as a scribe (clerk) and translator in the "Al-daera al-Sunni", and then he held the position of

¹ The Jubbah: It is a general dress, and most of the "Jubbah" have long and wide sleeves and open from the front. It contains golden ribbons that adorn the hem of the "jubbah" from the bottom as well as the sleeves. The "jubbah" is decorated with thin and wavy brown stripes (lines), and later became the approved uniform and garment for mosque preachers. The "Jubbah" has a different types, some of which have a thick cloth, and some of them have a light cloth. Type of the "Jubbah" is back to the social status of its owner. It is made of "silk" or "wool". As for the "jubbah", which is made of "Antaby" is lined and has a wide sleeves. Al-Rubaie 2013: 127. Cosgrave, 2000: 205.

² Al-Rubaie 2013: 127.

³ Naseem 1983: 54.

⁴ El souriany 1955: 50.

⁵ Naseem 1983: 55.

head of the Registry in railway. He was the destination of senior foreigners and Khawajas in Egypt to learn Arabic and French. After his death, a poetry book was issued to him in the name of "Al-Rawd Al-Arid Diwan. In 1924, "Iskandar Efendi Cosman" was died.¹

3.3. The third stage starts from 1924 to 1952: At this stage there was a development in education in the Amiri (governmental) and private schools, the Egyptian Amiri (governmental) University was established additional to Cairo University, issued many laws related to the development of education.

Coptic clerks learned the Arabic language at Al-Azhar Mosque, they also learned English and French and they proved their presence, ability and skills in banks, factories and foreign companies.

3.4. The fourth stage starts from 1952 to 1981: During this stage, a great opening occurred for the Egyptians to the West, and the words "katib" scribe or clerk and "effendi" began to decrease and dwindle, and a word of "Astaz" was used instead of them as a result of the change in the level of education and its sophisticated. Therefore, the construction of "al-kitab" and its function began disappeared, in addition to the number of Schools of all kinds in Egypt began to spread alongside universities.²

IV. DESCRIPTION STUDY

No. of line	Document No. 1 [Figure 1]	NO. of words
1	EGYPTIAN STATE No. 1 نمرة مسلسلة	4
2	مصلحة تلغرافات وتليفونات الحكومة المصرية	7
3	TELEGRAPHS AND No. 06166 رخصة جهاز	3
4	BROADCAST لاسلكي للاستقبال	3
5	RECEIVER LICENCESE	2
6	Issued in pursuance of the Royal Decree of 10 th	10
7	May 1926, governing Radio-Electric communication and subject to the conditions of Ministerial	18
8	Arrêté No. 11 of 1926 as amended by Arrêté No. 39 of 1933.	18
9	Expiry date of license 193....	4
10	Designation of the premises where the apparatus will be installed	10
11	in a house al Eiomara street Deirut.	26
12	Full name Fahmy Eff. Mikhail	7
13	Nationality Egyptian	12
14		4
15		

¹ Heyworth Dunne 1941: 64.

² Naseem 1983: 54.

16	Address of licensee Barclays Bank delegate at Deirout	عنوانه: مندوب بنك باركليز بديروط	11
17			2
18	Is authorised to install and use a broadcast receiver	بمقتضى هذا رخصنا بتركيب واستعمال جهاز لاسلكي لاستقبال في المحل المبين بعالية	22
19	solely for the reception of broadcasting as described in	على أن يكون استعماله لهذا الجهاز مقصورا على استقبال الإذاعات اللاسلكية العامة المشار إليها بالمادة ٣ من المرسوم الصادر بتاريخ ١٠ مايو سنة ١٩٢٦	22
20	Article 3 of the Decree of 10 th . May, 1926. Date stamp of Issuing office	وقد دفع الرسم الذي قدره ٨٠٠٠ مليم.	26
21	The payment of the fee of 800 milliemes is hereby acknowledged.		11
22	NO. of valve positions..... (Receipts on reverse).	عدد مواضع الصمامات سنه (الإبصالات على ظهر الرخصة)	15
23	For inspector General of telegraphs and telephones Gorgi Gabrial Shehata.	عن مفتش عام التلغرافات والتليفونات جورجي غيريال شحاته	18
24	Serial No. of previous license: Nil	النمرة المسلسلة للرخصة السابق صرفها لا يوجد	13
25	Expiry date of pervious license193....	تاريخ انتهاء الرخصة السابق صرفها سنة ١٩٣...	13
26	Date of issue 28 January 1935.	تاريخ إعطاء الرخصة ٢١ يناير سنة ١٩٣٥	13
27	Signature of licensee	إمضاء حامل الرخصة	8

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 26.8× 16.8 cm
- Number of lines: 27
- Kind of document: license
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- color of ink: black
- Date: 28 January 1935
- The sender: TELEGRAPHS AND TELEPHONES
- The addressee: Fahmy Eff. Mikhail
- From: Assiut Governorate
- To: Deirout
- Language: English, Arabic, Franch (Ministerial Arrêté)
- Watermark: The license has watermark on shape of plant decoration (half palm tree).it is repeated in various parts of license, the watermark is clearly shown in bright light. (Fig. 1b)
- Signature: include of Signature of licensee (Fahmy Eff. Mikhail)
- Content of the license: This license Contain of the accept the Egyptian government of telegraphs and telephones, grant Fahmy Eff. Mikhail delegate of Barclays bank, license to have broadcast receiver at Deirout in the branch of Barclays bank. The license bears two signatures, the first for inspector General of telegraphs and telephones Gorgi Gabrial Shehata. The second signature for licensee Fahmy Eff. Mikhail delegate of Barclays bank.

[Figure 1] A. Face of Broadcast receiver license B. Back of Broadcast receiver license in the name of Fahmy Effandy Mikhaeel delegate of Barclays bank at Deirout, dated in 1935. It is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 2 [Figure 2]	Number of words
1	ختم المكتب نو التاريخ	
2	مصلحة تليغرافات وتليفونات الحكومة المصرية	5
3	EGYPTIAN STATE A 07117	4
4	TELEGRAPHS AND TELEPHONES	3
5	Office date Stamp	3
6	إيصال عن رسوم رخصة جهاز لاسلكي للاستقبال	7
7	RECEIPT FOR BROADCAST LICENCE FEES	5
8	Name of Applicant: اسم الطالب فهمي أفندي ميخائيل منزله شارع الأُمراء بديروت	12
9	Address: العنوان موظف بنك باركليز بديروت	6
10	Date of payment: تاريخ الدفع ٢ يوليو سنة ١٩٣٧	9
11		2
12		2
13	License fee: قيمة الرسم المقرر عن الرخصة	8
14	Fee for valve positions: قيمة الرسم المقرر عن الصمامات	9
15	Total: الجملة	3
16		2
17		0
18	Amount in word: القيمة بالكتابة جنيه ومائه مليم لا غير	10
19		1
20	For Inspector General: عن المفتش العام	6
21	The fees shown above have been: قيمة الرسوم الموضحة أعلاه هي:	11
22	Received for renewal of license: عن تجديد رخصة نمرة ٦١٦٦	11
	No.	

23	Until.....	تنتهي في ١٨ يناير ١٩٣٨	6
24	This receipt is to be kept with the license and produced: -	هذا الإيصال يجب حفظه مع الرخصة وتقديمه: -	18
25	(a) When required for examination by an inspector or other authorised official.	(أ) إذا طلب الإطلاع عليه أحد المفتشين أو أي موظف آخر مسئول.	23
26	(b) When further renewal is required.	(ب) إذا أريد تجديد الرخصة	11
27		يملاً هذا الفراغ إذا أبرز الطالب رخصة للتجديد. وفيما عدا ذلك يشطب هذا الفراغ بواسطة الموظف الذي	17
28		يصرف الرخصة. وسترسل الرخصة أو أخطار التجديد إلي الطالب بطريق البريد في الوقت المناسب.	14
29	This section to be completed when applicant produces a license for renewal in all other cases, this		17
30	section is to be struck out by the issuing official, and all license or notification of renewal will be posted the applicant in due course)		20
31		تنبيه - يستعمل كربون بوجهين	4
32 use two sided carbon paper		5

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 22.8× 15.7 cm
- Number of lines: 27
- Kind of document: Receipt fees.
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- color of ink: black
- Date: 2nd July 1937
- The sender: EGYPTIAN STATE TELEGRAPHS AND TELEPHONES
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Unknown
- To: Deirout Al Mahatta (Deirout station)
- Language: Arabic and English
- Translate:

Applicant: Fahmy Effendi Mikhail, his home is Princes Street in Deirout

Address: Barclays Bank employee in Deirout

Payment date: 2nd July 1937

Content of the license: This receipt Contain of request renewal the license to use the BROADCAST RECEIVER which privet the Barclays Bank. Fahmy Mikhael delegates of Barclays bank introuduced the request who wrote on the receipt above with red pen:" Please renew the license today, Fahmy Shaker 38/1/983". We are noting he wrote the date of day wrongly 38, maybe he meant 28.

As well we noted use the Kobai pen or an indelible pencil also is known a copying pencil or chemical pencil to fill the data of the request. The receipt of payment is bearing a signature one of employs, who is performing the inspector general or vice inspector general. we are understanding from that, the inspector general is not found in the branches' offices. we can read the name of employ from his signature. He is called "Gawargy".

[Figure 2] Receipt for broadcast license fees, in the name of Fahmy Effandy Mikhaeel employee of Barclays bank at Deirout, dated in 1937. It is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 3 [Figure 3]	Number of words
1	R.C ALEXANDRIA NO. 92	6
2		3
3	From	6
4	(Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and overseas)	10
5	With which is AMALGAMATED	7
6	The ANGLO- EGYPTIAN Bank, limited	5
7	Telegraphic Address	2
8	BARCLAOM	1
9	Dear Sir,	2
10	Leave 1938	2
11	Kindly note that your leave this year has been	9
12	provisionally sanctioned for the period from the 20 th June	10
13	to the 5 th July, 1938, both dates inclusive.	9
14		2
15		1
16		1

Your faithfully

 Manager

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 13.8× 21.7 cm
- Number of lines: 16
- Kind of document: Memorandum
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: Cotton
- Date: 22 Feb. 1938
- The sender: Barclays Bank

- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Cairo
- To: Deirut Shoonah master
- Language: English
- Signature: include Signature of manager.
- Content of the speech: This memorandum Contained of reply to Fahmy Mikhail one of shoona staff Barclays Bank, who required to get leave, therefor the manager of Barclays Bank tell him his agree to grant him the leave which had been provisionally sanctioned for the period from the 20th June to the 5th July, 1938, both dates inclusive. The letter includes signature of the manager in write hand with black ink.
- It was also noticed that there was a seal in blue ink in the middle of the paper from the top is slant has a sentence consisting of three words with blue ink: "staff private and confidential" that stamp give us concept of significance to this letter.

[Figure 3] Memorandum from manager of Barclays bank to employee Fahmy Mikhail, dated on 22/2/1938, stamp with phrase: "staff private and confidential". It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 4 [Figure 4]	Number of words
1	EGYPTIAN STATE TELEGRAPHS AND TELEPHONES	مصلحة تليغرافات وتليفونات الحكومة المصرية 10
2	BROADCAST	رخصة جهاز 3
3	RECEIVER LICENCESE	لاسلكي للاستقبال 4
4	Issued in pursuance of the Royal Decree	معطاه تطبيقاً للمرسوم الملكي الصادر بتاريخ ١٠ مايو 15
5	of 10 th . May 1926, governing Radio-Elec-	سنة ١٩٢٦ بشأن تنظيم المواصلات اللاسلكية وبالشروط المنصوص 15
6	tric communication and subject to the	عليها في القرار الوزاري رقم ١١ لسنة ١٩٢٦ 14
7	conditions of Ministerial Arrêté	والمعدل بالقرار الوزاري رقم ٣٩ لسنة ١٩٣٣. 14

No. 11 of		
8	1926 as amended by Arrêté No. 39 of 1933.	9
9	Expiry date of license.....	10
10	No. of valve positions.....	10
11	١/٣٨ ٥ ق. ٦١٦٦٦	4
12	حضرة المحترم فهمي أفندي ميخائيل	5
13	منزل بشارع الأمراء – بديروط المحطة	5
14	Is authorised to install and use a	13
15	broadcast receiver at the address	15
16	tioned solely for the reception of	13
17	casting as described in Article 3 of	21
18	Decree of 10 th . May, 1926.	5
19	تاريخ دفع الرسم المقرر	9
20	Date of payment of fee	8
21	١٩٣٨/٢/٢٥	4

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 24.7× 15.5 cm
- Number of lines: 21
- Kind of document: license of telegraphs and telephones
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Kind of paper: Hemp
- Color of ink: black
- Date: 3rd September 1939
- The sender: EGYPTIAN STATE TELEGRAPHS AND TELEPHONES
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Unknown
- To: Dayrout Al Mahatta (Dayrout station)
- Language: Arabic and English
- Content of the license: This license Contain of the accept the Egyptian government of telegraphs and telephones, grant Fahmy Eff. Mikhail delegate of Barclays bank, license to have broadcast receiver at Deirout in the branch of Barclays bank. In the center of the license inside rectangle wrote in Arabic language in three lines:
 - 1- "1/38 61666 BC 5
 - 2- Mr. Honorable Fahmy Effendi Mikhail
 - 3- House on Princes Street - in Dayrout Al Mahatta (Dayrout station)"

In left side of the license there is signature for inspector general and the stamp of telegraphs and telephones. In the other side there is expire date of license. Next to that there are conditions of license which wrote from below and a back in Arabic and English language.

[Figure 4] A. Face of broadcast receiver license. B. Back of broadcast receiver license in the name of Fahmy Effandy Mikhael employee of Barclays bank at Deirout - El Omarae St. (Princes Street), dated in 1938. It is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. Researcher photography - first published.

No. of line	Document No. 5 [Figure 5]	Number of words
1	Memorandum	1
2	From Assiut 14 th Dec. 1938	6
3	(Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and overseas) To Mr. Fahmy Mikhail	10
4	With which is AMALGAMATED Deirut Agency	6
5	The ANGLO- EGYPTIAN Bank, limited	5
6	Telegraphic Address	2
7	BARCLAOM	1
8	Dear Sir,	2
9	We have the pleasure of informing you that our local Head office	12
10	have granted you an increase of LE. 10 p.a. as from 1 st January next year.	16
11	Therefore, as from that date your annual salary will be as under:	12
12	LE. 180. Per annum.	4
13	Your faithfully	2
14	Yours faithfully <i>Fahmy Effandy Mikhael</i> MANAGER.	1
15	Manager	1

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 13.8× 21.7 cm
- Number of lines:16
- Kind of document: Memorandum
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Date: 14 Dec. 1938
- The sender: Barclays Bank
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail

- From: Cairo
- To: Deirut Agency
- Language: English
- Signature: include Signature of manager Mr. Crouch.
- Content of the speech: This letter contains of decision the local Head office, which granted Mr. Fahmy Mikhail an increase of LE. 10 p.a. as from 1st January next year. Therefore, as from that date his annual salary will be as under: LE. 180. per annual. But notice in the end of the decision word "annum" maybe mean "annual" it was writing wrong. The decision includes signature of manager, wrote with black ink.

[Figure 5] Memorandum from manager of Barclays bank to employee Fahmy Mikhail, it dated in 14/12/1938. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 6 [Figure 6]	No. of words
1	R. ALEXANDRIA NO. C 92 (L.H.O) Assiut No. 400	8
2	TELEGRAPHIC ADDRESS Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and overseas)	8
3	"BARCLADOM" (INCORPORATED IN UNITED KINGDOM WITH LIMITED LIABILITY)	9
4	ASSIUT	1
5	CODES: "BENTLY'S" 1 ST EDITION	3
6	LIEBER'S FIVE LETTER	8
7	A.B.C.5 TH EDITIONS	4
8	ASSIUT, 16 th March, 1939.	3
9	EGYPT	2
10	Mr. Fahmy Mikhail, Shoonah Master, Staff,	1
11	Deirut Agency.	2
12	Dear Sir,	2
13	In reply to your letter of the 25 th ult. we would inform	11
14	You that the dates fixed for your 1939 leave have been changed as	13
15	follows:	1
16	June 16 to July 2 nd 1939 inclusive,	7

17	i.e. you should report back for duty to Deirut Agency on the 3 rd	13
18	July 1939.	2
19	Yours	2
	faithfully	
20	Yours faithfully, <i>Mikhail</i> MANAGER.	1
21	MANAGER.	1

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 27.6× 21.5 cm
- Number of lines:21
- Kind of document: official letters
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Date: 16th March, 1939
- The sender: Barclays Bank
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Assiut
- To: Deirut Agency
- Language: English
- Signature: include Signature of manager.
- Content of the speech: This letter is reply of Barclays Bank to Fahmy Mikhail’s letter. Which is wrote it on 25th. He requested a leave, and then he asked again to alternate the time of leave to be from June 16 to July 2nd 1939 inclusive. The bank gave him a permit to leave his work, but he should present report back to do his duties to Deirut Agency on the 3rd. I think this letter show the accurate arrangement and rules that Coptic clerk follow it, at any foundation affiliated it.

[Figure 6] Official letter from manager of Barclays bank to employee Fahmy Mikhail, it dated on 16/3/1939. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 7 [Figure 7]		Number of words
1	R.C	ALEXANDRIA NO. 92 Assiut No. 400	Memorandum 1
2	From		Assiut 14/ 6/ 39. 6
3	(Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and overseas)		To Mr. Fahmy Mikhail 10
4		With which is AMALGAMATED	Deirut Agency 6
5		The ANGLO- EGYPTIAN Bank, limited	5
6		Telegraphic Address	2
7		BARCLAOM	1
8	Dear Sir,		2
9		We enclose herewith a cash voucher for 14.683/1000 representing	2
10		your salary of this month which you are auhtorised to cash in advance.	12
11		Kindly return to us the enclosed salary receipt duly signed.	16
12			Your faithfully 2
13			Yours faithfully, MANAGER. 1
14			MANAGER. 1

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 21.7 × 13.8 cm
- Number of lines:14
- Kind of document: Memorandum
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Date: 14/ 6/ 39.
- The sender: Barclays Bank
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Assiut
- To: Deirut Agency
- Language: English
- Signature: include Signature of manager Mr. Dllumnd
- Content of the speech: Department of account inform Fahmy Mikhail with his salary it became 14.683/1000. The Bank asks him to return the enclosed salary receipt duly signed.

[Figure 7] Memorandum from manager of Barclays bank to employee Fahmy Mikhail, it dated on 14/6/1939. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 8 [Figure 8]	Number of words
1	R.C ALEXANDRIA NO. MEMORANDUM 92 Assiut No. 400	8
2	From 22 nd January, 1942.	4
3	(Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and To The clerk in charge, overseas)	11
4	(INCORPORATED IN UNITED Deirut Agency. KINGDOM WITH LIMITED LIABILITY)	9
5	ASSIUT Branch	2
6	Telegraphic Address	2
7	BARCLAOM	1
8	D. C. O. 305 ESP.	5
9	Dear Sir,	2
10	We have pleaser in informing that the board have	9
11	Granted increases in salaries to date from 1 st January 1942, as	11
12	Showen below. we shall be glade if you will advise the staff con-	13
13	cerned accordingly: -	2
14	Name Increases as from 1.1. 1942 Salary as from 1. 1.1942 Allowance as from 1.1. 1942	19
15	MIKHAIL, F. £ .5. - £ .190.- --	5
16	Plus, the usually High Cost Yours	7
17	faithfully Of living Allowance.	1
18	Yours faithfully [Signature] MANAGER.	1
	MANAGER.	1

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 13.8× 21.5 cm

- Number of lines:18
- Kind of document: official letters
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: Cotton
- Date: 22nd January, 1942.
- The sender: Barclays Bank
- The addressee: To the clerk in charge.
- From: Assiut
- To: Deirut Agency
- Language: English
- Signature: include Signature of manager Mr. Dllumnd

Content of the speech: Department of account that follow Barclays bank sent to the clerk in charge who was work in Deirut agency, who is charged about an accounts and salaries of the bank, to inform him that administrative of Barclays Bank grant Fahmy Mikhail increase or allowance on his salary, amount 5 pounds in year to be his salary 190 pounds in year from 1st January 1942. We must useful from this document with three important points: -

- 1-The clerk in charge about the accounts and salaries is unknown to the Bank.
- 2-The bank approve and specific the arrangement and rules of salaries to every persona, yearly.
- 3-The Increase in salary of Fahmy Mikhail in great value amount is evidence a place of Coptic clerk Fahmy Mikhail Affendy, who was in charge about Deirut agency and the Bank confident in his administrative, he also in charge to delivered the employees or clerk the work or transmit them inside the agency as benefit the work.

[Figure 8] Memorandum show annually increases in Fahmy Mikhail salary; it dated on 22/01/1942. It is kept by the descendants. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 9 [Figure 9]	No. of words
1	R.C ALEXANDRIA NO. 92 (L.H.O)	8
2	ASSIUT NO. 400	3

3	TELEGRAPHIC ADDRESS	Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and overseas)	8
4	"BARCLADOM" ASSIUT CODES:	(INCORPORATED IN UNITED KINGDOM WITH LIMITED LIABILITY)	9
5			1
6	"BENTLY'S" 1 ST EDITION		4
7	LIEBER'S FIVE LETTER	ASSIUT, 23 rd September 1943.	8
8	A.B.C.5 TH EDITIONS	EGYPT	7
9	Mr. Fahmy Mikhail,		2
10	Shoonah Master,		2
11	Deirut.		1
12	Dear Fahmy Eff.,		3
13	In reply to your letter of yesterday's date,		8
14	the undersigned understands that Mr. Crouch replied to you		9
15	verbally to your letter of the 23 rd July last, when he advised		13
16	you that it was not possible for you to be transferred to an-		13
17	other Branch, we further understand that you were offered a		10
18	transfer to Abnoub Shoonah which would have enabled you to		10
19	send your children to Assiut secondary school, but that you		10
20	were unwilling to accept this transfer.		6
21	The matter of moving your family to Minieh is		9
22	entirely your own affair, but we regret that whilst we should		11
23	be willing to allow you to go to Minieh occasionally at the		12
24	week-end to visit your family, in no circumstances can we give		12
25	you permission to be absent from Deirut for this purpose every		11
26	week – end, of which please take careful note.		8
27		Yours faithfully	2
28			1
29		A/Manager	2

Description of document:

- Dimensions:26.6× 21.3 cm
- Number of lines:29
- Kind of document: official letter
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Date: 23rd September 1943
- The sender: Barclays Bank
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Assiut
- To: Deirut.
- Language: English
- Signature: include Signature of A/Manager.
- Content of the speech: in that official letter the administration of Barclays Bank replied on Fahmy Eff. one of Shoonah staff, who was request to be transferred to another Branch, because, he was want to move his family to Minia government to send his children at secondary school. But his request is refused because the Bank offered

to him transfer to Abnoub Shoona which would have enabled him to send his children to Assiut secondary school, whilst he refused that offered.

[Figure 9] Official letter from manager of Barclays Bank to Fahmy Mikhail one of Shoona staff, who is requested transfer to another branch, dated in 23/9/1943. It is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 10 [Figure 10]	No. words
1	R. ALEXANDRIA NO. MEMORANDUM	8
	C 92 Assiut No. 400	
2	From 5 th April, 1946	4
3	BARCLAYS BANK (DOMINION, COLONIAL, AND OVERSEAS)	6
4	من بنك بركليز (للممتلكات البريطانية المستقلة والمستعمرات والخارج) To Mr. Fahmy Mikhail,	12
5	(INCORPORATED IN UNITED KINGDOM WITH LIMITED LIABILITY)	7
6	ASSIUT Branch ASSIUT	3
7	فرع	1
8	Dear Sir,	2
9	<u>LOCAL STTAF PROVIDENT FUND.</u>	4
10	We are pleased to inform you that it has been decided	11
11	That you may subscribe to the local staff provident fund and we shall	13
12	Be glad to know if you wish become a member of this fund.	13
13	Briefly, the advantage is that 4 % of your salary is	10
14	Deducted monthly and placed to your credit in this local staff	11
15	Provident fund. We would urge you to join the fund. If you so desire	14
16	Please sing and return to us the enclosed form.	9
17	Yours faithfully	2

18	Yours faithfully, MANAGER.	1
19	MANAGER.	1

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 14 cm × 21.9cm
- Number of lines:19
- Kind of document: Official letter
- Writing type: Typography and hand write
- Color of ink: Black
- Kind of paper: **Rag paper**
- Writing type: Typewriter (machine) with black ink.
- Date: 5th April, 1946
- The sender: Barclays Bank
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Assiut Branch
- To: Mr. Fahmy Mikhail,
- Language: Arabic and English.
- Signature: include Signature of manager.

Content of the speech: LOCAL STTAF PROVIDENT FUND informs Fahmy Mikhail if he desired to join to local staff provident fund as a member. The advantage is that 4 % of his salary monthly. They were required him to singe the form and send to them again.

[Figure 10] Memorandum from manager of Barclays bank to employee Fahmy Mikhail, it dated on 05/04/1946. It is first published.

No.
of
line

Document No. 11 [Figure 11]

No. of
words

1	D.C.O 305 Esp.	5
2	Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and overseas)	6
3	إلى حضرة المحترم To.....	(INCORPORATED IN UNITED KINGDOM WITH LIMITED LIABILITY) 11
4	ناظر شونة روض الفرج والخارج)	بنك بركليز (للممتلكات البريطانية المستقلة والمستعمرات 13
5	(مؤسس في المملكة البريطانية بمسؤولية محدودة) 6
6		فرعBRANCH القاهرة 3
7		تاريخ 1946 ٢ سبتمبر ١٩٤٦ 5
8		بعد التحية — 2
9		حامل هذه لويس أفندي يوسف سليمان قد تعين من اليوم موظفاً بالشونة 12
10		لمراقبة عملية تفريغ الغلال من الموردرات والسكة الحديد ومساعدتكم في أعمال 11
11		الشونة. 1
12	بنك بركليز بالقاهرة	3
13		1
14	عن المدير	2

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 13.4 × 21.9cm
- Number of lines:14
- Kind of document: Official letter
- Writing type: Typography and hand write
- Color of ink: Blue
- Kind of paper: **Rag paper**
- Writing type: Typewriter (machine) with blue ink.
- Date: 3rd September 1946
- The sender: Barclays Bank
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Cairo
- To: Rod El Farag
- Language: Arabic and English.
- Signature: include Signature of vice manager.
- Content of the speech: this is official letter is sent to Mr. Fahmey Mikhail from his manager at Barclays Bank to deliver the work in the Shoona (granary) to the new employee Luis Effendi Yusuf Suleiman, to supervise the supply of grain from suppliers and the railways, and also assist you in the Shoona works (granary).

The letter was written in Arabic language using blue ink, and reads as follow:

Cairo Branch

3rd September 1946

After salutations

“The bearer of this, Luis Effendi Yusef Suleiman, has been appointed from today as an employee of the Shoona to monitor the process of unloading the grain from the suppliers and the railways and to assist you in the work of the Shoona (granary)”.

Barclays Bank in Cairo

Vice manager

And although the letter was written in Arabic, the deputy director signed it in English, because he was a British man.

[Figure 11] Official letter from manager of Barclays Bank to supervisor of the Shoona, Rod El Farag branch to deliver the work to a new employee, it dated on 3/9/1946. It is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 12 [Figure 12]	Number of words
1	BARCLAYS BANK (DOMINION, COLONIAL, AND OVERSEAS)	6
2	LOCAL HEAD OFFICE	30 th SEP. 1947
3	ALEXANDRIA	1
4		0
5	LOCAL STTAF PROVIDENT FUND.	Mr. F. Mikhail
6		(Member's name)
7		Cairo Branch
8	Credit Balance on 30 th September 1946. Brought Forward	L.E4 149
9	Total monthly subscribe 31-10- 1946 to 30-9-1947	9 297
10	Interest on account to date at 4% per annum	- 336
11		L.E 13 812
12	Less Income Tax	
13		L.E 13 812
14		0
15	FOR BARCLAYS BANK (DOMINION, COLONIAL, AND OVERSEAS)	7
16		0
17		LOCAL DIRECTOR.
18	D.C.O. 137 ESP.	5

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 14 × 21.9cm
- Number of lines:18
- Kind of document: Official form
- Writing type: Typography
- Color of ink: Black
- Kind of paper: **Rag paper**
- Writing type: Typewriter (machine) with black ink.
- Date: 30th SEP. 1947
- The sender: Barclays Bank
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Alexandria
- To: Cairo Branch
- Language: English.
- Signature: include Signature of local director.

Content of the speech: Content of the speech: its official form delivered to Mr. Fahmy Mikhail to sign it if he desired to subscribe in LOCAL STTAF PROVIDENT FUND, showed in it, value of advantages that would be add to his salary monthly 4% annual, But I think there are something wrong, if you make account $9.297 \times 4\% = 371.88$ not 336 as what is mentioned in the form, without clear if was there any reduces or commissions or taxes.

BARCLAYS BANK (DOMINION, COLONIAL AND OVERSEAS)
LOCAL HEAD OFFICE
ALEXANDRIA

30 SEP 1947 19

LOCAL STAFF PROVIDENT FUND Mr. F. Mikhail
(Member's Name)
Cairo Branch

Credit Balance on 30th September 19 <u>46</u>	Brought Forward	£	4	179
Total monthly subscriptions <u>31-10-</u> 19 <u>46</u> to <u>30-9-</u> 19 <u>47</u>			9	297
Interest on account to date at <u>4</u> % per annum			-	336
	£		13	812
Less Income Tax				
	£		13	812

FOR BARCLAYS BANK (DOMINION, COLONIAL AND OVERSEAS)

D.C.O. 173 ESP. LOCAL DIRECTOR'S

[Figure 12] official letter from chief accountant of Barclays bank to employee Fahmy Mikhail, it dated on 30/09/1947. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 13 [Figure 13]	Number of words
1	The chief Accountant Cairo 8 th , June, 1950	8
2	Barclays Bank D.C.O,	5
3	Cairo,	1

4	Dear Sir,	2
5	I beg to bring by the present my case hoping you will be kind	14
6	enough to extend to be me your assistance.	8
7	As you know, sir, I am until the time of writing considered	12
8	by the bank as a member of Shoonah staff although I am working in	14
9	Cairo office as a clerk and supervisor of the depots under the bank's	13
10	control for about 2 years and I believe that I have performed my duties	14
11	as a clerk in a very satisfactory way.	8
12	Now I feel that I am really in need of a favour which I am	15
13	asking and which I tendered to the chief Accountant in December last,	12
14	namely, my transfer from the shoonah staff to clerical staff which	11
15	means quite a lot for me either from the stand point of view of	14
16	allowances or privileges. This I ask for the same of my 7 children	13
17	who are in the university, secondary and primary schools and whose	11
18	expenses are a heavy burden for me which I cannot at present afford.	13
19	I hope you will be kind enough to see your way to back me up	15
20	in my request and am certain that by your valuable help I will be	14
21	granted this favour.	3
22	I beg to enclose the copy of my previous letter of the 7 th	14
23	December last on the same subject.	6
24	I thank you very much for taking the trouble of considering	11
25	my case.	2
26	Your faithfully	2
27		1
28	F. Mikhail.	2
29	Merchandise Department	2

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 27.2 × 21.4 cm
- Number of lines: 28
- Kind of document: A personal letter
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Date: 8th, June, 1950
- The sender: Fahmy Mikhail
- The addressee: The chief Accountant at Barclays Bank
- From: Cairo
- To: Cairo
- Language: English
- Signature: include Signature of Fahmy Mikhail.
- Content of the speech: in this letter Mr. Fahmy Mikhail write to chief accountant Barclays Bank beg to him to make favour to Mr. Fahmy Mikhail, who was work in Cairo office as a clerk and supervisor of the depots under the bank's control for about 2 years. But considered by the bank as a member of Shoonah staff. He wanted to have assistance of the chief accountant to promotion namely, which means quite a lot for him either from the stand point of view of allowances or privileges.

Mr. Fahmy Mikhail proved in his letter that he deserves to indeed promotion when he mentioned this sentence in this letter: "I believe that I have performed my duties as a clerk in a very satisfactory way".

Mr. Fahmy Mikhail also tried to marvelous the chief accountant to help him, he mentioned in his letter: "I ask for the same of my 7 children who are in the university, secondary and primary schools and whose expenses are a heavy burden for me which I cannot at present afford".

[Figure 13] Official letter from Fahmy Mikhail to the chief accountant, who is beg to help him to transfer from Shoona stuff to clerical stuff, it dated on 8/7/1950. It is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 14 [Figure 14]	Number of words
1	Fahmy Mikhail,	2
2	C/O Merchandise Dept.,	3
3	Cairo Branch.	2
4	12 th January 1951	3
5	The chief Accountant,	3
6	Barclays bank (D.C & O)	5
7	Cairo	1
8	Dear Sir,	2
9	I beg to submit my case for your kind attention hoping that	12
10	you will kindly recommend it for consideration.	7
11	I was appointed in 1932 as a Shoonah master at Deirout at the	13
12	time when there was no agency yet. I accepted this post after obtaining	13
13	the promise of late Mr. Amin shams, the sub-Manager of Assiout Branch at	13
14	that time, to be given the position of clerk in charge in the new	14
15	agency to be opened at Deirout, which was similar to my previous post	13
16	at the Banco Italo Egiziano and which I occupied for 7 years. I worked	14
17	at the Shoonah as a clerk and handled the cash movement of the cereals	14
18	and cotton clients of whom were Messrs. Pispinis Bros. who used to	12
19	encash daily about L.E. 4000 to L.E. 6000.	8
20	After about 6 months, the agency was opened at Deirout and a	12
21	clerk in charge was appointed in spite of the promise I hade from the	14

22	Sub- Manager, on the ground that I should spend some more time to know	14
23	the system of work.	4
24	I acted as a Shoonah Master, delegate of the Bin Bank at Pispinis	13
25	Bros Ginning Factory and Assistant clerk in charge in the same time,	12
26	which post is occupied at present by 2 persons I have always done my	14
27	best to perform all my duties in satisfactory manner and I was fully	13
28	confident that my reward would be a promotion a senior post on the	13
29	clerical staff.	2
30	I was disappointed when in 1940 the H.C.L. was paid to the	12
31	staff and I learned that there were different catagories of clerical and	12
32	non-clerical staff, a fact which I never knew before and which I never	13
33	expected. Late Mr. N. Shenouda of Assiout Branch advised me verbally that	12
34	my case would be considered at the end of the war as the time was not	16
35	suitable for discussions in such matter. I waited patiently for my	11
36	transfer.	1
37	In 1945 I was transferred from Dierout to Assiout Branch in	11
38	the merchandise department and the bills department. I was also charged	11
39	to go to Koussieh Shoonah for 2 or 3 days weekly to estimate the value	15
40	of the Durra Eweiga received under the government Scheme and to effect	12
41	payment of the value there of to the cultivators. I was also charged	13
42	to do so the same at Abou Tig Agency. My work was merely clerical such	15
43	as B/C settlements, out movement, Journal and Remitters books.	9
44	In 1946 I have been advised by Assiout Manager that a Shoonah	12
45	Master was required for Rod El Farage and it was natural that I jumped at	15
46	the occasion as my children were on their way to finish their secondary	13
47	education and they had to continue their higher education at Cairo.	11
48	Although I was transferred to Cairo, I was not granted an increase in	13
49	the high cost of living which remained at the rate of the provinces	13
50	I.E.LE. 25 less that of Cairo.	6
51	In January 1949 I was transfer to Cairo Branch as a super-	12
52	visor of the stores under the Bank's control of the Societe D'Avances	12
53	D'Avances commercials and the Trading corporation of Egypt and to take part	12
54	in the clerical work of the merchandised department, Which I had per-	12
55	formed perfectly.	2
56	On 7 th December 1949 I submitted a request asking the favour	11
57	of transferring me to the clerical staff to help me in supporting my	13
58	family but I was not lucky to receive the approval of the bank to my	15
59	request.	1
60	Furthermore, the increase of my salary I received in that year for LE. 12.00	14
61	was met by a decrease for the same amount in my displacement allowance, thus	14
62	I have been deprived of any actual increase to help me to meet the	14
63	exorbitant high cost of living in Cairo.	7
64	My case was submitted to Mr. Haines the chief Accountant at that	12
65	time and he was kind enough to advise me that my case would be considered	15
66	the following year.	3
67	I finally resort to your kindness to help me and I am full of hope	15
68	that my transfer to clerical staff will be approved on your	11
69	recommendation. In this connection I would mention that the following	10
70	gentlemen were transferred from the Shoonah staff to the clerical staff:	11
71	1-Mr. Alfi Dimitri of Maghagha. 2- Riad Kamel of Beni Mazar.	11
72	3- Youssef Nakhla of Samallut.	5
73	You will notice, Sir, that my case is no exception and from my	13
74	dossier you will decide that I have quite a reasonable background	11
75	which qualifies me for such a transfer. Awaiting your kind.	10
76	Reply, please accept my thanks for your kind attention.	9
77		2
78		
79		

Yours obediently

F. MIKHAIL.

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 32.9 × 21.6 cm
- Number of lines: 79
- Kind of document: petition letter
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Date: 12th January 1951
- The sender: Fahmy Mikhail
- The addressee: The chief Accountant at Barclays Bank
- From: Cairo
- To: Cairo
- Signature: Include Signature of Fahmy Mikhail.

This letter is petition to the chief accountant of Barclays Bank from Fahmey mikhail, who explained in it his case, from appointed Date in Barclays bank until date of write his letter as follow:

1-He appointed in 1932 at Shoonah master in Deirout, Assiut government before establishment the agency. 2- He accepted this post after obtaining the promise of the sub-Manager of Assiut Branch (Mr. Amin shams). 3- The sub-manager promises Fahmey Mikhael the position of clerk in charge in the new agency to be opened at Deirout. 4- He worked at the Banco Italo Egiziano and which he occupied for 7 years before worked Barclays Bank. 5- He charged about the cash movement of the cereals and cotton clients. 6- Deirout branch used to encash daily about L.E. 4000 to L.E. 6000 at the time.7- After 6 months from appointed Fahmy Mikhael the agency was opened at Deirout and appointed a clerk in charge instead of him (This is what makes her sad) 8- He acted delegate of the Bin Bank at Pispinis Bros Ginning Factory and Assistant clerk in charge in the same time (he means done his best). 9- He was hope to his promotion a senior post on the clerical staff. 10- He was disappointed when in 1940. 11- Mr. N. Shenouda of Assiut Branch advised him verbally that my case would be considered at the end of the war. (This means that everything was suspended due to the war). 12- In 1945 he was transferred from Dierout to Assiut Branch in the merchandise department and the bills department. 13- He was also charged to work in Koussieh Shoonah to estimate the value of the Durra Eweiga received under the government Scheme and paied the money to the cultivators. 14- He was also charged to do so the same at Abou-tig Agency. 15- In 1946 he transferred to Shoonah master at Rod El Farage in Cairo, this is good opportunity to his children they had continue their higher education at Cairo. 16- He Complained not granted an increase in his salary in spite of the high cost of living in Cairo. 17- He mentioned the expenses of living in the provinces less than Cairo with rate 1:25. 18- He was worked a supervisor of the stores under the Bank's control of the Societe D'Avances commercials and the Trading corporation of Egypt in Cairo. 19- On 7th December 1949 he submitted a request asking the transferring him to the clerical staff, but his request is refused. 20- He requested increase in his salary to meet the exorbitant high cost of living in Cairo. 21- Mr. Haines the chief Accountant advise him that his case would be considered the following year. 22- in finally, he requested the chief Accountant a recommendation to transfer to clerical staff and mentioned three cases transferred to clerical staff.

Noticed in signature of Fahmey Mikhail, that he wrote his name with his hand "Michel" by ink pen, while he wrote his name printing "Mikhail", this is the interpretation in Arabic language, but Michel his name in English language.

[Figure 14]: Petition to the chief accountant of Barclays Bank from Fahmey Mikhail, who explained in it his case, from his nominate date in Barclays bank until date of write his letter, it dated on 12/1/1951. It is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 15 [Figure 15]	No. of words
1	سجل تجاري اسكندرية رقم ٩٢ (المركز الرئيسي المحلي) Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and overseas)	14
2	القاهرة رقم ٣٩٣٧ (INCORPORATED IN UNITED KINGDOM WITH LIMITED LIABILITY)	10
3	R ALEXANDRIA NO. 92 (L.H.O) بنك بركليز (للممتلكات البريطانية المستقلة والمستعمرات والخارج)	13
4	C Cairo NO. 3937 (مؤسس في المملكة البريطانية بمسؤولية محدودة)	9
5	TELEGRAPHIC ADDRESS:	2
6	"BARCDOMCRO" Cairo	2
7	CODES: Cairo, 8 th June 1953 القاهرة في	7
8	"BENTLY'S" 1 ST EDITION EGYPT	5
9	Mr. Fahmy Mikhail	3
10	Cairo	1
11	Dear sir,	2
12	I have received your letter of the 6 th of June and	7

13	advise you that its contents will be borne in mind when considering	10
14	Increases as from the first of January next.	8
15		2
16	Yours faithfully,	1
	Chief Accountant	
17	CHIEF ACCOUNTANT	2

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 26.5× 21.6 cm
- Number of lines: 14
- Kind of document: official letter
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Kind of ink and its color: black
- Date: 8th June 1953
- sender: Chief accountant
- Consignee: Mr. Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Cairo
- To: Cairo
- Language: English
- Signature: signature of chief accountant
- Content of the speech: Contained this letter reply of Barclays Bank D.C.O to Fahmy Mikhail on his letter. The chief accountant informs him that annual increase from the first of January next. It is important in this study, it informs us about important information like salaries system and annual increases in Barclays bank.

[Figure 15]: Official letter from Chief accountant to Fahmy Mikhail, it dated on 8/7/1953. It is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. It is first published.

No · of lin e	Document No. 16 [Figure 16]	No. of word
1	سجل تجاري اسكندرية رقم ٩٢ (المركز) Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and	14

	الرئيسي المحلي	overseas)	
2	القاهرة رقم ٣٩٣٧	(INCORPORATED IN UNITED KINGDOM WITH LIMITED LIABILITY)	10
3	ALEXANDRIA NO. R. C 92 (L.H.O)	بنك بركليز (للممتلكات البريطانية المستقلة والمستعمرات والخارج)	13
4	Cairo NO. 3937	(مؤسس في المملكة البريطانية بمسؤولية محدودة)	9
5	TELEGRAPHIC ADDRESS:		2
6	"BARCDOMCRO" Cairo		2
7	CODES:	Cairo, 14 th October 1953	7
8	"BENTLY'S" 1 ST EDITION	EGYPT	5
9	The Shoonah Master,		3
10	Rod el Farag,		1
11	SHOONAH.		2
12	On my visit to the shoonah last month I was surprised to		7
13	Find that you not stacking cereals in accordance with the requirements of the government wheat scheme and that the cereals were not adequately protected from damp.		10
14	On my instructions Mr. Fakhry Tadros visited you yesterday And confirms that poles are still not being properly used. I Must stress that the instructions are to be observed and that it Is not sufficient for wooden poles to be laid parallel on the Ground underneath the sacks. other wooden poles must be placed At right-angles underneath those running the length of the poles So that the sacks are raised from the ground by the height of Two wooden poles. Cereals which have not been correctly stacked in this way Are to be re-stacked and you are to advise this office as and When each lot is in your opinion stacked in accordance with the Regulations. Please also inform me why you did not follow out My instructions at the time they were given.		8
15			2
	<u>CHIEF ACCOUNTANT.</u>		
17	CHIEF ACCOUNTANT		2

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 26.5× 21.6 cm
- Number of lines: 14
- Kind of document: official letter
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Kind of ink and its color: black
- Date: 14th October 1953
- sender: Chief accountant
- consignee: The Shoonah Master
- From: Cairo
- To: Rod El Farag Shoonah master

- Language: English
- Signature: signature of chief accountant
- Content of the speech: This letter is very important, as it contains very important information. It is a blame and reproach to Michael Effendi, who did not follow the instructions of his direct manager (the head of accounts), and who was dissatisfied when he visited the shuna with the method of storing wheat according to the government's instructions, and Michael Effendi's failure to use the wooden poles correctly. He gave instructions to store wheat properly. In order to ensure that Michael Effendi adhered to the instructions, on the second day, he sent Fakhri Tadros Efendi to ensure compliance with instructions for storing wheat. But he was upset because Michael Effendi did not follow the instructions. So he sent him this letter, informing him of the correct method of storing wheat and that it should be above the ground by two poles high in two rows. He asked Michael Effendi to tell him why he did not obey the instructions and carry them out.

[Figure 16]: official letter from chief accountant of Barclays bank to employee Fahmy Mikhail, Rod El Farag Shoonah master, it dated on 14/10/1953. It is first published.

No. Of line	Document No. 17 [Figure 17]	No. of words
1	19 September 1955	3
2	The manager,	2
3	Barclays Bank D.C.O.	5
4	Cairo	1
5	Dear sir,	2
6	I am in receipt of your letter dated 16 th instant,	10
7	advising me of my placing on pension as from 1 st December 1955,	12
8	I take this opportunity to offer my thanks and gratitude for your	12
9	best wishes to me and shall be much obliged if you will kindly	13
10	communicate my thanks to Head office and local Head office.	10
11	I remain, Sir,	3
12	Yours faithfully	2
13	Fahmy Mikhail,	2
14	Rod El Farag Shoonah – Master.	4

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 27.7× 21.7 cm
- Number of lines: 14
- Kind of document: official letter
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Kind of ink and its color: black
- Date: 19 September 1955
- The sender: Fahmy Mikhail
- The addressee: The manager Barclays Bank
- From: Rod El Farag Shoonah master
- To: Cairo
- Language: English
- Signature: without signature
- Content of the speech: Contained in this letter reply of Fahmy Mikhail on letter of the manager of Barclays Bank D.C.O. Who tell him a date of his pension as from 1st December 1955 and present his thanks and gratitude to head office and local head office, but he does not signature on this letter. Which have important information, as he finished his letter a phrase "I remain, Sir" is he mean he will continue in his work. I think he would continue in work after his pension.

[Figure 17]: official letter from employee Fahmy Mikhail, Rod El Farag Shoonah master to manager of Barclays bank, it dated on 19/09/1955. It is first published.

No.	Document No. 18 [Figure 18]	No. of words
1	19 th September 1955	3
2	The manager,	2

3	Barclays Bank D.C.O.	2
4	Cairo	1
5	Dear sir,	2
6	With reference to your letter of the 16 th instant, I wish	11
7	to commute a part of my pension for the maximum possible cash payment,	12
8	with my very best thanks.	5
9		Yours faithfully
10		Fahmy Mikhail,
11		Rod El Farag Shoonah Master,

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 27.7× 21.7 cm
- Number of lines: 11
- Kind of document: Official letter
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Date: 19th September 1955
- The sender: Fahmy Mikhail
- The addressee: The manager Barclays Bank
- From: Rod El Farag Shoonah master
- To: Barclays Bank in Cairo
- Language: English
- Signature: without Signature
- Content of the speech: Contained in this letter a desire Fahmy Mikhail which he wrote to the manager of Barclays Bank D.C.O. on 19th September 1955 which had been wishing commute a part of his pension for the maximum possible cash payment. But I noticed the letter had been without signature maybe the cause back to Have a spelling error or wanting to modify the writing formulation, or he had withdrawn his request.

[Figure 18]: official letter from employee Fahmy Mikhail, Rod El Farag Shoonah master to manager of Barclays bank, it dated on 19/09/1955. It is first published.

No.	Document No. 19 [Figure 19]	No. of words
1	19 th , October, 1955	3
2	The chief Accountant	3
3	Barclays Bank D.C.O,	5

4	Cairo	1	
5	Dear sir,	2	
6	I thank you for your kind letter of 17 th , instant, and	11	
7	note that my annual pension will amount to LE. 207.500 m/ms. reduced	13	
8	by LE.51,875 m/ms. for the cash payment.	8	
9	As the cash payment of LE.417.335m/ms. would appear to be	11	
10	smaller than the amount expected. I should be grateful if you	11	
11	would kindly advise local head office that the amount of cash	11	
12	cash payment expected was over LE. 500	7	
13	A waiting your reply, with my best thanks in advance.	10	
14		Yours obediently	2
15		Fahmy Mikhail,	2
16		Rod El Farag Shoonah Master,	4
17		Cairo	1

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 27.7× 21.7 cm
- Number of lines: 17
- Kind of document: letter
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Kind of ink and its color: black
- Date: 19th October 1955
- The sender: Fahmy Mikhail
- The addressee: The Chief Accountant Barclays Bank
- From: Rod El Farag Shoonah master
- To: Cairo
- Language: English
- Signature: without signature
- Content of the speech: Contained in this letter reply of Fahmy Mikhail on letter of the manager on 17th, instant, (17th of this month, which it wrote in it the same letter, October) tell him about account his pension salary which was LE. 207.500 m/ms. then it were deducting LE.51, 875 m/ms from the amount, and he complains that the amount commute of his pension is little, which is LE.417.335m/ms. he would expect to be bigger than this amount. He had suggested being over LE 500.

19th. October, 1955.

The Chief Accountant,
Barclays Bank D.C.O.,
Cairo.

Dear Sir,

I thank you for your kind letter of the 17th. instant, and note that my annual pension will amount to L£.207.500m/ms. reduced by L£.51.875m/ms. for the cash payment.

As the cash payment of L£.417.335m/ms. would appear to be smaller than the amount expected. I should be grateful if you would kindly advise Local Head Office that the amount of cash payment expected was over L£.500.-

Awaiting your reply, with my best thanks in advance.

Yours obediently,

FAHMY MIKHAIL,
Rod El Farag Shoonah Master,
Cairo.

[Figure 19]: official letter from employee Fahmy Mikhail, Rod El Farag Shoonah master to Chief accountant of Barclays bank, it dated on 19/10/1955. It is first published.

No. of line	Document No. 20 [Figure 20]	No. of words
1	Barclays Bank D.C.O. Formerly باركليز بنك دي. سي. أو. سابقاً	12
2	سجل تجاري اسكندرية رقم ٩٢ (المركز الرئيسي المحلي) Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and overseas)	14
3	القاهرة رقم ٣٩٣٧ (INCORPORATED IN UNITED KINGDOM WITH LIMITED LIABILITY)	10
4	R.C ALEXANDRIA NO. 92 (L.H.O) بنك بركليز (للممتلكات البريطانية المستقلة والمستعمرات والخارج)	13
5	Cairo NO. 3937 (مؤسس في المملكة البريطانية بمسؤولية محدودة)	9
6	TELEGRAPHIC ADDRESS: "BARCDOMCRO" Cairo	2 2
7	CODES: Cairo, 9 th November, 1955 في القاهرة	7
8	"BENTLY'S" 1 ST EDITION EGYPT	5
9	Mr. Fahmy Mikhail	3
10	Cairo	1
11	Dear sir,	2
12	With reference to your letter of the	7
13	19th October, 1955 we are informed by Head office that	10
14	the calculation for commutation is governed by the	8
15	age and status (I.e., "clerical" or "Shoonah" category)	8
16	of the individual concerned. The calculations at the	8

17	present time are governed by tables which have been	9
18	supplied by the bank's Actuaries based on the actuarial	9
19	categories of staff in the Bank's employ.	7
20	In your case, being classified as "shoonah"	7
21	staff and taking into consideration your age of 60.1/2	10
22	years at retirement, the rate applied was IE.8.045 for	10
23	each IE.1. – surrendered on your nominal pension.	8
24		2
25		1
26		2

Yours faithfully

CHIEF ACCOUNTANT

Description of document:

- Dimensions:26.7× 21.2 cm
- Number of lines:26
- Kind of document: Official letter
- Writing type: typography and hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: Cotton
- Date: 9th November, 1955
- The sender: Barclays Bank
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: Cairo
- To: Cairo
- Language: English and Arabic
- Signature: include Signature of chief accountant at Barclays Bank.
- Content of the speech: Mr. Fahmy Mikhail presented an inquiry to chief accountant of Barclays bank ask about the way of calculate for commutation of his pension, So the chief accountant sent to him a reply with this official letter explained that the way of calculate did by the bank's Actuaries and according to the actuarial categories of staff. In Fahmy case his age is 60 years and six months, so he deserved 8.045 Egyptian pounds for each one pound from his salary.

[Figure 20] Official letter from the chief accountant to Fahmy Mikhail, who replied on his claim which written on 19/10/1955, this letter dated in 9/11/1955. It is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. It first published.

No. of line	Document No. 21 [Figure 21]	Number Of words
1	عزيزي فهمي أفندي	3
2	حامل هذا منير أفندي توفيق حنا قد تعين	8
3	لمساعدتكم في الشونة من تاريخه	5
4	فالرجا تحديد واجباته ليكون مسؤول أمامكم	6
5	ولكم الشكر المستخدم	3
6	شنودة	1

Description of document:

- Dimensions: 27.02× 21.02 cm
- Number of lines: 6
- Total of words: 26
- Kind of document: Official letter
- Writing type: hand write
- Color of ink: black
- Kind of paper: **rag paper**
- Date: without Date
- The sender: the employee Shenouda
- The addressee: Fahmy Mikhail
- From: unknown
- To: unknown
- Language: Arabic
- Signature: include Signature of the employee Shenouda.
- Translate:

1 **Dear Fahmy Effendi,**
 2 A man which holding that, is Munir Effendi Tawfiq Hanna. He has been
 3 appointed.
 4 To help you in the granary (Shoonah) of date of today
 5 Please specify his duties to be accountable to you
 6 Thank you, employee
 Shenouda

- Content of the speech: Barclays Bank sent a new employee to be assistant with Mr. Fahmy Mikhail and under his charge; his name is Munir Effendi Tawfiq Hanna. The letter was written with hand the employee Shenouda Effendi.

[Figure 21] Unofficial letter from Shoonoda to Fahmy Mikhail, who gives recommendation to new employee Munir Effendi Tawfiq is kept by the descendants of Fahmy Mikhail. It is first published.

V. ANALYZED STUDY

5.1. WRITING TOOLS WHICH USED IN THAT PERIOD

5.1. 1. PAPER:

The Coptic clerks had used to write this letters aforementioned, on Kind of paper is known with rag paper. It is also known as rag stock paper, is made a reuse the cotton from used old cloth or as known cotton linter (rag) as the primary material. Important documents are often printed on rag paper (cotton paper), because it is known to last many years without deterioration. Cotton paper is superior in both strength and durability and color for many years, which may contain high concentrations of acid, and also absorbs ink or toner better. it was produced this kind of paper different grades.

In the first, the cotton was used with a mixture of silk to make paper called "Carta Bombycina". Since 1800s, fiber crops such as flax fibres or cotton from used cloths (rags) were the primary material source to made rope and cotton paper.¹ By the turn of the 20th century, most paper was made from wood pulp, but cotton is still used in specialty papers. As cotton rags now often contain synthetic fibres, papermakers have turned to second-cut cotton linters as raw material sources for making pulp for cotton papers.² That it is obvious in document No. 1 as according the examination. [Figure 22]

[Figure 22]1- A 100-millimeter microscope shot showing cotton fibers and skill in Document No.1. A 20 millimeter microscope shot showing cotton fibers and skill in Document No. 1. [Figure 1]

¹ Sadiq 2010: 69. Al-Samarrai 2001: 287.

² Nanko & (des) 2005: 62

The first paper mill was established in Italy in 674 AH / 1275 AD and it were called the paper mill because it worked like mills with the power of water. The mills consist of heavy hammers that break up raw materials, such as worn-out fabrics, cotton rags, ropes, wood, etc., and a solution of lime (sulfite) is added to them to bleach them in order to extract the paper.¹

5.1.2. The materials of paper:

5.1.2..1. Cotton: The fibres are the purest form of cellulose available to the paper maker, yielding 98% of pure cellulose. They are in the form of tubes averaging 25/32mm long and 0.025mm wide. The material comes to the paper maker as linter (the part of the plant unsuitable for textiles) and as rags. Upon examination of Document No.3 and No.20, [Figure 3, 20] it was found that the paper was made of cotton. [Figure 23]

[Figure 23]1- A 20-millimeter microscope shot showing cotton fibers in Document No.3.
2-A 20 millimeter microscope shot showing cotton fibers in Document No. 20.

5.1.2.2.. Hemp: Is obtained chiefly from worn-out ropes or sails that are discarded from ships as now useless but are very valuable to the paper maker (hence the saying ‘Money for old rope’). The fibres contain about 75% of cellulose. Hemp is a strong fibre which is why it is used for rope and makes strong paper, especially wrapping paper. Its brown colour could not be bleached, so paper made from hemp was brown — a tradition followed today, which is why wrapping paper is brown. That is clearly in document No. 4 [Figure 4] and document No. 3 [Figure 3] upon examination A 20 – 50 millimeter microscope shot showing hemp fibers and some other tissues, so the examination shows the effects of insect damage. [Figure 24]

[Figure 24] 1, 2 A 50-millimeter microscope shot showing hemp fibers in Document No.4.

¹ Al-Samarrai 2001: 270.

3, 4 A 20, 5 millimeter microscope shot showing hemp fibers and a spot maybe a blood in Document No. 4.

5.1.2.3.. Jute: Is obtained from used sacking and contains about 60% of cellulose.

5.1.2.4.Flax: In the form of linen from rags “Esparto” fibres come from the leaf of this grass that grows in a hot and dry climate, and to minimise the loss of water the leaf curls round to form a tube. The grass is harvested by pulling (not cutting) so the bales that arrive at the paper makers contain a lot of sand on the roots which has to be washed away. The yield of fibre is less than 50%.

5.1.2.5.Rags: At one time the most prolific source of material was rags. First, they had to collect of discarded and soiled clothing, then after the material had been roughly washed, they had to sort it, rejecting the non-cellulose items such as silk, wool, and, later, synthetics. Buttons, metal fasteners and elastic had to be cut off. Finally, did cut the rags into small pieces on a knife. Only now were the rags ready for the chemical treatment and beating that turned them into pulp. Upon examination of Document No.1 [Figure 1] it was found that the paper was made of rage. [Figure 25]

[Figure 25] A 20-millimeter microscope shot showing rags material in document No.1.

[Figure 26] 1. A 50-millimeter microscope shot showing the tissues of paper in case the flexed document No.4. 2. A 100-millimeter microscope shot showing the tissues of paper in case the torn document No.3.

5.1.3. Ink:

The invention of ink is a precursor to humankind, it is invented in ancient Egypt circa 5,000 y ago, is the established to humankind commits words to writing. That is revealed complex composition of inks. Highlighted by the presence of iron and another material, the red color can be attributed to the use of ocher. Unexpectedly, lead is regularly present in the blue, red and black inks and is associated to phosphate, sulfate, chloride, and carboxylate ions. That lead was probably used as a drier rather than as a pigment, similar to its usage in 15th century Europe during the development of oil paintings.¹

¹ Christiansen & (des) 2020: 27826.

Ink is a gel, sol, or solution that contains at least one colorant, such as a dye or pigment, and is used to color a surface to produce an image, text, or design. Ink is used for drawing or writing with a pen, brush, reed pen, or quill. Thicker inks, in paste form, are used extensively in letterpress and lithographic printing.

The oldest type of ink is Indian or Chinese ink, which is made of black ivory and mixture of gum or glue, which dates back to about 2500 BC, in addition to inks that are made from various natural materials such as berries, tree bark, linseed oil and soot. As for the inks that were known before that, they were made from galls that grow in oak trees.

Ink was used in Ancient for writing and drawing on papyrus from at least the 26th century BC. Egyptian red and black inks included iron and ocher as a pigment, in addition to phosphate, sulfate, chloride, and carboxylate ions; while, used the lead as a drier.¹

In the 15th century, a new type of ink had to be developed in Europe for the printing press by Johannes Gutenberg.² According to Martyn Lyons in his book *Books: A Living History*, Gutenberg's dye was indelible, oil-based, and made from the soot of lamps (lamp-black) mixed with varnish and egg white. Two types of ink were prevalent at the time: the Greek and Roman writing ink (soot, glue, and water) and the 12th century variety composed of ferrous sulfate, gall, gum, and water. Neither of these handwriting inks could adhere to printing surfaces without creating blurs. Eventually an oily, varnish-like ink made of soot, turpentine, and walnut oil was created specifically for the printing press

Thousands of formulations for the ink industry have been developed over the centuries and the standard black ink containing tannic acid, which may have been known in the second century, is more common.

Ink formulas vary, but commonly involve two components:

Colorants - Vehicles (binders)

Inks generally fall into four classes:³

Aqueous – Liquid – Paste - Powder

Printing made the written word more widespread than ever and yet it was still in the hands of a few elites. Until the typewriter appeared in the 1860s and made printing usable in commercial communications, this required another development in ink as the Hansen typewriter was invented for writing in (1865) and mass production began in (1870), followed by models for a number of companies other manufacturer. In most cases, typewriters relied on a piece of cloth soaked in ink. The pigmented ink is designed to stay wet on the tape with the addition of castor oil, but it dries up on contact with the paper. In later designs, notably the "IBM Selectric" typewriter, strips of polymer tape coated with pigment was used. In both cases, when the embossed characters collide with the paper, the transfer of ink is transferred to the paper.

¹ Christiansen & (des) 2020: 27825.

² *Kassia* 2016: 271–273.

³ Kipphan 2001: 130–144.

- 1- A 5 millimeter microscope shot showing carbon ink in document No.7.
- 2- A100 millimeter microscope shot showing purple ink in document No.4.
- 3- A20 millimeter microscope shot showing red ink in document No.9.
- 4- A100 millimeter microscope shot showing iron ink in document No.1.
- 5- A50 millimeter microscope shot showing blue ink and carbon ink in document No.4.
- 6- A50 millimeter microscope shot showing blue ink and carbon ink in document No.20.

Examining the documents revealed that he used different types of ink, such as carbon ink, iron ink document No.7 [figure 7], and colored ink (purple, red and blue), as in Document No. 4, [Figure4] he used carbon ink for writing, and purple ink for sealing, and Document No.1 [Figure1] used iron ink. Document No. 9, 20 [Figure 9, 20] use iron ink with red ink to show and clarify a word or sentence. [Figure 27] Sometimes, he had used blue ink to write the letter completely as appear in document No. 11 [Figure 11].

Upon examination of the inks in document No. 8 [Figure 8] that penetrated the tissues of the paper the most, the iron ink was found to be more penetrating and stable than the carbon ink, the reason for this is the presence of a high cotton pile, which helped absorb the ink in a large amount, especially iron ink. [Figure 28]

[Figure 28]: A20 millimeter microscope shot showing iron ink in document No.8 more penetrating and stable inside tissue of paper.

The penetration of iron ink appears more in paper made of cotton material or with a higher percentage of cotton than in other materials. Even the degree of its penetration into the tissue of the paper makes it appear as if the words were written and then the paper was printed on it with carbon ink. The carbon ink appears on top of the iron ink. [Figure 29] Because the degree of penetration of carbon ink into the tissues of the paper is less than that

of iron ink. But the degree of absorption and penetration of carbon ink varies depending on the type of paper. [Figure 30]

[Figure 29]: A20 - 100 millimeter microscope shot showing iron ink in document No.1 more penetrating and stable inside tissue of paper more than carbon ink.

[Figure 30]: 1, 2. A 20 - 50 millimeter microscope shot showing the absorption degree the cotton paper to Carbon ink in document No.20 - 3, 4. A 5 - 50 millimeter microscope shot showing the absorption degree the rage and hemp paper to Carbon ink in document No.1, 4.

An examination of Document No. 8 shows the difference between the types of ink, that is, between carbon ink and iron ink, more clearly, as we notice that carbon ink was used in the printer, while iron ink was used in handwriting.

[Figure 30] 1 A 100 millimeter microscope shot showing the different between Carbon and Iron ink in document No.8. 2. Showing the different between Carbon and Iron ink in document No.7.

Also, the reliance in the paper industry on textile materials has led to the paper being easily exposed to insect damage and acidity stains that damage the papers and thus the loss of important writings and information on them. We see this clearly in Document No. 1 and 15. [Figure 31]

[Figure 31] 1-5 A 20 and 100 millimeter microscope shot showing the damage of insect effects in document No.1. 6. Showing acidity stains in document No.15.

5.1.4. Kobia pencil:

An indelible pencil also is known a copying pencil or chemical pencil.¹ It's named in the Arabic language "Kobia" or "Cobia", maybe derived from word "copy" [Figure 32]. That pencil was containing lead matter and a dye. The lead is fabricated by adding a dry water-soluble permanent dye to powdered graphite—used in standard graphite pencils—before binding the mixture with clay.²

In the 1870s, started use an indelible pencil and were originally marketed for copying documents, especially for making permanent copies of a permanent original. This was achieved by creating a hand-written document using a copying pencil, laying a moist tissue paper over the document and pressing down with a mechanical press. The water-soluble dye in the writing would be transferred in its mirror image to the tissue paper, which could then be read in verso by holding it up to a light source.

The most commonly used dye was aniline, which produced a stain that was bright purple, mauve, or some color in between, depending upon the manufacturer.³ Since the aniline dye was poisonous to humans, many injuries and illness related to copying pencils were reported in the medical literature, especially in the late-19th and early-20th centuries.

[Figure 32] Showing the type of Kobia pencil in document No. 2 [Figure 2]

¹ Tolhausen, A.: «Chemical writing without ink», [Pharmaceutical journal and transactions](#), John Churchill, London: 1858: 228. [Link](#)

² Dube 1998: 17. Owen 2004: 40–42. Stroud 1985: 58.

³ Owen 2008: 41-48. [link](#)

5.1.5. Sizes and names of paper

From an early period, sizes of paper sheets had become more or less standardized, although each manufacturer had its own variations depending on the size of the moulds. The size and type of paper were denoted by names which were associated with the watermark, such as crown, helmet, plants and phrases. The size of a writing paper was various. We do not find an equal (one) size between these documents of Barclays Bank, but tried every company to be distinguished with size of its paper. We found size of "Wemmel bank" sheet is 27.6× 21.5 and 26.6× 21, 3 [Figure 6, 9], size of "Abremill bond" sheet is 26.5× 21.6 and [Figure 15, 16], size of "Pamel's helmet Special" sheet is 27.7× 21.7 [Figure 17, 18, 19], size of "Merrille no. 1" is 27.2× 21.2 [Figure 21]. But regarding to the half of sheets, it is approximately one size "21.7 × 13.8" such as a sheet has a watermark "LOB... N W BANK" document No.3 [Figure 3], a document No. is "12× 21.9" and a document No.8 is "13.8×21.5". And due to various the size of sheets the governments were imposes taxes on a writing paper according to size of sheet as clear in the table.

5.1.6. Watermark method for documenting paper type and manufacturer:

Although the concept of a watermark is simple but the technical expertise needed to produce a clear and satisfactory image should not be underestimated. By only incidentally was it found to possible making the watermark. The dandy roll has raised portions in the form of the watermark that displace some of the fibres, which are replaced by water that quickly drains away; consequently, the paper at the watermark is slightly thinner and so let's more light through. The pieces (called bits) used to make the watermark were initially pieces of wire which were sewn onto the dandy roll (or with hand-made paper, onto the inside of the bottom of the mould) with fine wire but were later (and still are) electrotypes soldered to the dandy roll. The purpose of a watermark was often to denote the size of the sheet and the name of its maker or the mill where it was made. It can give a clue to the country of origin, the manufacturer and other useful information. Some watermarks include a date but care must be taken in interpreting it. It may be the year when the paper was made but sometimes the paper maker did not change it and went on using the same date in subsequent years.

Marks were added invisibly to the paper during its manufacture to distinguish between the different types of paper, the manufacturers and the country of manufacture, and we do not know exactly when the idea of watermarks appeared, or who invented this idea. But what is known and common is that Italy was the first to invent watermarks in Europe.

As for the oldest paper in the Arab world, watermarks were found on it. It was simple slanting lines, which were made in the eastern Islamic world, specifically in the seventh century AH / thirteenth century AD.

Qasim al-Samarrai expressed the chance of making watermarks in the Arab world by saying: "The Arabs, spontaneously or deliberately, were aware of the action that results from copper wires, leaving in the paper lines that can be seen through exposure to the sun or bright light. These lines were initially invented in a way Primitive in paper at the end of the seventh century AH and were known as water lines.

The appearance of water lines on paper increased in the first half of the eighth century AH / fourteenth century AD, so European craftsmen imitated them and added to it a special sign for their factories.

The oldest manuscripts known to the Arab and Islamic world are a manuscript preserved in the Public Treasury in Rabat No. 529D dated 750 AH / 1349 AD, and another manuscript is preserved in the Egyptian Endowment Library No. 668 dated 809 AH / 1406 AD.

These marks are made by making the design that is chosen by shaping by wire and fixed on the surface of the papermaking mold with flexible threads. When the fibers flow on the

surface of the mold, they gather more in the spaces between the bends of the design than they gather at the top of the wire itself, forming from the fibers a negative image of it in the thickness of the paper around the design, you see Only when you see the paper backlit.

These methods have been followed in the manufacture of watermarks in official papers until the twenty Century, whether governmental or private letters, to prevent their forgery. Through the study of these documents, I found many different watermarks in their shapes and locations, as writings in English or Latin letters, floral decorations, and human drawings.

On document No. 1 "Broadcast receiver license" found as look like decoration of Arabic "Arabesque"¹ or "Tauriquos"². **[Figure 33]** This decoration look like palm leaves and their halves were used, which moved from the Hellenistic period to the Roman, Sassanid, Byzantine, and finally the Islamic era, which reached the height of its prosperity in the Mamluk era. They were used in the decoration of arabesques on mosques such as the Al-Tanbagha Mosque.³It is most likely that the Seljuk Turks, when they settled in the country of Rome (Asia Minor), transferred this decoration and called it "Rumi".⁴

[Figure 33] A watermark of the document No. 1, drawing by the researcher.

On document No. 2, 4 broadcast receiver license it dated on 18/1/1938, and broadcast receiver license fees it dated on 25/2/1938 there is three Latin capital letters E.S.R as a watermark, it is brief of words: " Egypt services of received". **[Figure 34]**

[Figure 34] Watermark document No. 2, 4, drawing by the researcher.

But on document No.3 "the Memorandum", it dated on 22/2/1938, Wrote on it as a watermark: "LOB..... N W BANK". **[Figure 35]** But some of letters from the first word disappeared. That is watermarked is prove of property this document to the bank. It is private papers with the administration of the bank was use by them only.

¹ Arabesque decoration is a name given by European historians to Islamic decorations that are characterized by the Samarra style of the 3rd century AH / 9th century AD, which includes decorations and geometrical or plant elements modified from nature, so that it has become difficult to return them to their initial origins, even if their affiliation to the plant family does not differ in it. Muhammad 1986: 201. For more on the arabesque decoration see: Hussein 1997: 60. Al-Mahdi 1993: 56 -57. Alois Regal, in his book "What is Style", which was published in Berlin in 1893, is considered the first scientist to define the word arabesque on a specific type of Islamic art decoration, describing it as a type of plant decoration far from natural origins, and it is appearing in the form of sequential dividing forked rings. Hussein 1987: 11.

² Tauriquos is the most appropriate and true word for this type of decoration, the most prominent of which is the phenomenon of growth. The Tauriquos is really a growth and reproduction. The word Tauriquos is still used in the Spanish language to this day to denote this decoration, and it is based mostly on plant decorative elements. Marzouk 1987: 11.

³ Shafei 1970: 221.

⁴Rumi's decoration consists of plant branches drawn in a special way that are not subject in their form, directions and growth to the system of nature. Which made it a special character. Hence, we are not mistaken if we call it the Ottoman Tauriquos decoration or the Ottoman arabesque. The name "Rumi" is derived from the word "Rumi", which means "Byzantine", which is used for this type of decoration. The Arabs used to call the Byzantines "Rumi". Marzouk 1987: 76.

LOB..... N W BANK

[Figure 35] watermark on "Memorandum", Wrote: LOB..... N W BANK, drawing by the researcher.

This watermark that indicates to property the bank to these papers appeared also on document No.6, 9 it dated on 16/3/1939 and 23/9/1943, "Official letter from manager of Barclays Bank to Fahmy Mikhail" wrote on it as a watermark "WEMMEL BANK". [Figure 36] Wemmel Bank now¹ is a big bank in Belgium in Brussels. I think, it is extension to the Wemmel bank in the past (the old). It is commercial Bank, and had been became a new name KBC Bank Wemmel, May be the Barclays bank was buying the papers which made particularly for Wemmel bank. It was a deal between them.

[Figure 36] shows a watermark on document No.6, 9. It wrote: WEMMEL BANK, Drawing by the researcher.

As for the document No.17, 18, 19 it dated on 19/9/1955 and 19/10/1955 "Official letter from Fahmy Mikhail to the chief accountant", it has a different and unique watermarked, wrote on it "Pamel's helmet Special", [Figure 37] addition to drawing head of a roman soldier who wear helmet instead of word of helmet. Pamel's special is mean private only to Pamel or it is property to Pamel. That back us to the concept or function from invent the watermark. The watermark function is a property proof and it is prevent the forgery.

[Figure 37] watermark on previous letter wrote: "Pamel's Special", with drawing head of a roman soldier who wear helmet.

On document No. 21 "unofficial letter from Shenouda to Fahmy Mikhail", wrote on it "Merrille no. 1" [Figure 38] that is brief to name of "Charles Merrille no.1". But I do not

¹«KBC Bank Wemmel»: <https://www.kbc.be/particulieren/nl/kantoor/4188-WEMMEL-DE%20LIMBURG%20STIRUMLAAN-26.html>, Accessed on 7/11/2023.

know exactly who Charles is? Maybe is the Manufacturer (factory owner) or maybe is Charles E. Merrill¹ (1885-1956) cofounder of Merrill, Lynch & Co. in 1914.

Merrill no.1

[Figure 38] watermark on document 21 wrote “Merrille no. 1”, drawing by the researcher.

On document No. 15, 16 and 20 it dated on 8/7/1953, 14/10/1953 and 9/11/1955 there is an important watermark, “ABERMILL BOND MADE IN GT BRITAIN”, [Figure 39] this sentence wrote on a writing paper as a watermark. On Thursday, February 21, 1929, a United Kingdom trademark registration was filed for ABERMILL BOND by Wiggins Teape Limited. The United Kingdom IP office has given the trademark application number of UK00000500247 in 1929. Now the current status of this trademark filing is dead. The correspondent listed for ABERMILL BOND is Potter Clarkson LLP. The ABERMILL BOND trademark is filed in the category of Paper Goods and Printed Material. It was a Writing paper made in Great Britain.²

[Figure 39] watermark on document No. 15, 16 and 20, it wrote "ABERMILL BOND MADE IN GT BRITAIN", drawing by researcher.

On document No. 8, it dated on 22/1/1942 there is an important watermark, expression here about quality and material of papers, the manufactory wrote in paper as a watermark a word “Strong”. It wrote in vertical position. [Figure 40]

STRONG

¹ Charles E. Merrill was born on October 19, 1885 in Green Cove Springs, Florida, USA the son of Dr. Charles and Octavia Wilson Merrill. His father, a local physician. He worked at Patchogue Mills; Merrill joined George H. Burr & Company in 1909. «Charles E. Merrill»: <https://www.encyclopedia.com/education/economics-magazines/merrill-charles>, accessed on 30/10/2023. He was an American philanthropist, stockbroker, and cofounder, with Edmund C. Lynch, of Merrill Lynch (previously called Charles E. Merrill & Co.). «Charles E. Merrill»: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Charles_E._Merrill, accessed on 30/10/2023.

² «ABERMILL BOND United Kingdom Trademark Information»: <https://www.trademarkia.com/uk/trademark-UK00000500247.htm>, accessed on 7/11/2023.

[Figure 40] watermark on document No. 8, it wrote "STRONG", drawing by researcher.

But on document No. 12 it dated 30/9/1947, wrote a watermark "VIOND" [Figure 41] first three letters wrote on the head of the document in vertical position and last two letters wrote on footer of the document. In fact I do not know who is VIOND? Or what is meaning VIOND? But i know that Vinod is an Indian name for males, it is still in use.¹

IV

DNO

[Figure 41] watermark on document No. 12, it wrote "VIOND", drawing by researcher.

5.1.7. Surnames:

5.1.7.1. Effendy:

Effendi or Effendy, a word was passed on Arabic language from Ottoman Turkish "Efendi" while the originally from Greek "αφέντης" which pronounce "aphentēs" which is meaning lord. Efendi is a title of nobility meaning lord, Commander² or master, especially in the Ottoman Empire lands and the Caucasus.³

It began to be used by the Ottomans in the second decade of the fifteenth century AD to refer to the educated person, as it replaced the similar word "Chalabi" or "Galabi" in the Turkish language, and affixed namely, Scientists, army officers from the rank of lieutenant to the Bekbashi, and senior Statesmen, then the title "Effendi" or "Effendina" became the official title of princes after the mid-nineteenth century AD.⁴

It is a title of respect or courtesy, equivalent a title "Sir" or "prince" in England. It was used in the Ottoman Empire and Byzantine Empire. It follows the personal name, when it is used, and is generally given to members of the learned professions (clerks, money exchanger, book holders) and to government officials who have high ranks, such as bey or pasha. It may also indicate a definite profession, as "hekim efendi", he is a chief physician to the sultan. In the modern age, the word changes to possessive form "efendim" which mean "my master", in formal discourse to express about more respect, when answering the telephone, and can substitute for "excuse me" in some situations (like asking someone to repeat something).⁵ The Republican Turkish authorities abolished the title circa the 1930s.⁶

The clerks' group was called "Effendia", and "Effendia" positions were hereditary and could be sold. They are headed by a person called "the first effendi" or "Al-rosnamji", who chooses from among the "effendia" and is appointed for life.⁷

To appoint "Effendi", he must be educated, master arithmetic and other matters related to financial management, and obtain the approval of "Al-Rosnamji". The "Effendi" used a specific type of script that is difficult and requires practice and training. It is called "Al-Qarmah" script.⁸

In our modern age, the job of the "Rosnamji" is equivalent the rank of "general financial director. The "Effandi" is specialized in the government's books and records everything

¹ «Vinod»: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vinod>, accessed on 31/10/2023.

² Al-Hilal 1903: 246 - 247.

³ El-Messiri 1997: 5.

⁴ Sabyan 2000: 34.

⁵ Chisholm 1911: 9, 10.

⁶ Shaw & Shaw 1977: 386.

⁷ Shalaby 1989: 14.

⁸ Shalaby 1989: 15.

related to taxes, the public treasury budget, state expenditures, the costs of state public projects, and others.

The "Al-Rosnamji" is affiliated him four "Afandia" who help him in managing all financial matters in the country. The first called "Bash Halfa", the second "Second Halfa", the third "Third Halfa", and the fourth "fourth Halfa" and they are responsible for preparing the taxes that must be paid by each Obligated owns state land. and many clerks and money-changers follow these, and they are Turks, Jews, and Copts.¹

5.1.7.2. Al Mohtarm (Respected)

A title that was given to the Mamluk princes in the Mamluk era, then it became called upon the common people as a kind of glorification and glorification. One of the oldest texts in which the surname of "El-Mohtaram", "The Respected" was mentioned is an inscription on a copper incense burner dated 675AH from Egypt, preserved in the British Museum, in the name of Prince Badr al-Din Beisri al-Zahiri al-Saidi al-Shamsi. The surname of "The Respected" was also found on the mausoleum of Prince Taybaga from the year 765 AH, and this indicates that this title was one of the titles of senior princes.²

5.1.7.3. Al Moustiakhdam (employee)

The user or employee: someone who performs paid work for the government or the like. Employee: A person who is assigned work to perform it according to his specialty in one of the government departments or other: An employee in the Ministry of Health, a government employee, an employee in the citizen service, the employee has fixed times for coming and leaving. Civilian employee: An employee who works in the civil service.

5.1.7.4. Sir,

Sir is a formal honorific address in English for men, derived from Sire in the High Middle Ages. Both are derived from the old French "Sieur" (Lord), brought to England by the French-speaking Normans, and which now exist in French only as part of "Monsieur", with the equivalent "My Lord" in English. Traditionally, as governed by law and custom, Sir is used for men who are knights and belong to certain orders of chivalry, as well as later applied to baronets and other offices. As the female equivalent for knighthood is damehood, the suo jure female equivalent term is typically Dame. The wife of a knight or baronet tends to be addressed as Lady, although a few exceptions and interchanges of these uses exist. Additionally, since the late modern period, Sir has been used as a respectful way to address a man of superior social status or military rank. Equivalent terms of address for women are Madam (shortened to Ma'am), in addition to social honorifics such as Mrs, Ms or Miss.³

5.1.7.5. Mr.

Mister, usually written in its contracted form Mr. or Mr, is a commonly used English honorific for men without a higher honorific, or professional title, or any of various designations of office.[1] The title Mr derived from earlier forms of master, as the equivalent female titles Mrs, Miss, and Ms all derived from earlier forms of mistress. Master is sometimes still used as an honorific for boys and young men.

The modern plural form is Misters, although its usual formal abbreviation Messrs derives from use of the French title messieurs in the 18th century.[2][5] Messieurs is the plural of

¹ Shalaby 1989: 15.

² Al-Basha 1989 460.

³ «Sir»: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sir>, accessed on 31/10/2023.

monsieur (originally mon sieur, "my lord"), formed by declining both of its constituent parts separately.

Historically, mister was applied only to those above one's own status if they had no higher title such as Sir or my lord in the English class system, that understanding is now obsolete, as it was gradually expanded as a mark of respect to those of equal status and then to all men without a higher style.¹

In the 19th century and earlier in Britain, two gradations of "gentleman" were recognized; the higher was entitled to use "esquire" (usually abbreviated to Esq, which followed the name), and the lower employed "Mr" before the name. Today, on correspondence from Buckingham Palace, a man who is a UK citizen is addressed with post-nominal "Esq", and a man of foreign nationality is addressed with prefix "Mr".

In past centuries, Mr was used with a first name to distinguish among family members who might otherwise be confused in conversation: Mr Doe would be the eldest present; younger brothers or cousins were then referred to as Mr Richard Doe and Mr William Doe and so on. Such usage survived longer in family-owned business or when domestic servants were referring to adult male family members with the same surname.²

5.1.7.6. Hazrat

It uses the title like an honorary title, which is one of the spatial euphemisms in the Mamluk era. Archaeological inscriptions indicate that it was used in the fourth century AH, and the Seljuks used it, and those of lower status than the ministers in the Ayyubid era addressed it, then it moved to the Mamluk era, and it was given to Sultan Qaytbay in the tomb of Prince Yaqub Shah in 901 AH. In the Mamluk era, it was used as a title among the titles of Christian kings, and it was the title of Patriarch of Egypt. Its uses were numerous in the Ottoman era, and it was used to refer to sultans, ministers, senior statesmen, and righteous, (Awliya' Allah). During the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, it was often followed by the word "Esteem" in official addresses and correspondence.³

5.1.8. Names of clerks mentioned in the documents:

5.1.8.1. Fahmy Effendi Mikhail:

He worked at the Banco Italo Egiziano and which he occupied for 7 years before worked Barclays Bank. He acted delegate of the Bin Bank at Pispinis Bros Ginning Factory and Assistant clerk in charge in the same time. He appointed in 1932 at Shoonah master in Dairout, Assiut government. He asked continuously for many years, to transfer from shoonah clerk to staff clerk. he was felt oppressed cause of his work in shoona. In 1945 he was transferred from Dierout to Assiut Branch in the merchandise department and the bills department. He was also charged to work in "Koussieh" Shoona to estimate the value of the Durra Eweiga received under the government Scheme and paid the money to the cultivators. 1946 he transferred to "Shoonah" master at Rod El Farage in Cairo. He was worked a supervisor of the stores under the Bank's control of the Societe D'Avances commercials and the Trading corporation of Egypt in Cairo. He had six children who are in the university, secondary and primary schools. We can understand from previously presentation; Fahmy Mikhail had many skills, ability, and good learning, to reach to prestigious position. He was known speaks and write the English and Italy languages. We do not know date of his death exactly. [Documents No. 1-22].

¹ Sengupta 2011: 278.

² «Mr. »: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mr.>, accessed on 31/10/2010.

³ Barakat 2000: 208, 209.

5.1.8.2. George Gabriel Shehata was employee in telegraphs and telephones [Document No.2].

5.1.8.3. Shenouda Effendi, employee (Clerk) of Barclays Bank. [Document No.21]

5.1.8.4. Mounir Effendi Tawfiq Hanna. [Document No.21]

5.1.8.5. Louis Effendi Yusuf Suleiman. [Document No.11]

5.1.8.6. Mr. Alfi Dimitri of Maghagha. [Document No.14]

5.1.8.7. Riad Kamel of Beni Mazar. [Document No.14]

5.1.8.8. Youssef Nakhla of Samallut. [Document No.14]

5.1.8.9. Fakhry Tadros employee (Clerk) of Barclays Bank from Cairo. [Document No.16]

5.1.8.10. Shenouda employee (Clerk) of Barclays Bank from Cairo. [Document No.21]

5.1.9. Subscriptions (Signatures)

The letters whether official or unofficial are contain a signature wrote in Arabic language of English language, the Arab scribes had signed on their letters also in English language that a proof on their state and position at Barclays bank. Often of signatures were used the iron ink. It is more absorption and penetrates in paper or anther meaning it is more stable. The next table is show the type of signatures and its drawing that showed names of managers of Barclays bank, chief accountant and employees.

Signature	professional	date	Docu ment No.
	Barclays Bank delegate at Deirout	28 January 1935	1
	For Inspector General	2 nd July 1937	2
	Manager	22 Feb. 1938	3
	For Inspector General	3 rd September 1939	4
Yours faithfully, MANAGER.	Manager	14 Dec. 1938	5
Yours faithfully, MANAGER.	Manager	16 th March, 1939	6
Yours faithfully, MANAGER.	Manager	14/ 6/ 39.	7
Yours faithfully, MANAGER.	Manager	22 nd January, 1942.	8
 A/Manager	A/Manager	23 rd September 1942	9
Yours faithfully, MANAGER.	Manager	5 th April, 1946	10
	Vice manager	3 rd September	11
	Local Director	30 th SEP. 1947	12

	Fahmey Mikhail Merchandise Dept.	8 th , June, 1950	13
	Fahmey Mikhail	12 th January 1951	14
 Chief Accountant	Chief accountant	14 th October 1953	15
	Chief accountant	14 th October 1953	16
	Chief accountant	9 th November,	20
	employee	Without date	21

5.1.10. Kind of letter:

The letters edited by Coptic writers varied between official letters and personal letters. As for official letters, they are of two types: letters sent to Barclays Bank, and letters issued by it.

As for the letters issued by the bank, they explain the precise administrative work system that the bank's management, clerks, and employees working in the bank go through. The accuracy of the bank in avoiding forgery by placing watermarks on its official papers, or perhaps these signs were placed by the owner of the company to identify his product. It was noted that all the letters issued by the bank were signed by the bank manager, the accounts manager, or the head of the department. It is the system that has been followed until this time in any sector that has a precise and disciplined administrative system.

These letters were permits to obtain leave or a permit to be absent, a letter appointing a new employee, a letter transferring one of the bank's employees to another branch, a letter of financial settlement, financial entitlements, or an official response from the bank to employee complaints and others.

Among the most important of these letters is the complaint submitted by Mikhail Fahmy Effendi to the bank manager, complaining that he works as an employee in the bank's Shoona (barn), and his level of education and experience qualifies him to work as a clerk in one of the bank's branches, not in the Shoona.

These letters clearly show the role of Coptic scribes, whether they wrote those letters, or implemented the decisions contained in them, or delegated the bank to one of its Coptic scribes to extract a telegraph license in his name for one of its branches far from the capital, such as the license issued in the name of Fahmy Mikhael Effendi in Dayrout, Assiut Governorate.

As for personal letters, which take an official form and are a set of complaints submitted by Fahmy Mikhail, one of the bank's clerks. In it he explains that he is supposed to be a clerk at the bank and not an employee in Shoona, and another complaint in which he seeks to be transferred from Assiut to Minya near his home, living and family, and a third complaint in which he complains that his salary does not cover the high living expenses in Cairo.

These correspondences had an important role in knowing accurate details about salaries, job grades for bank employees, the titles of each job grade, and the difference between writers and employees. The status of the work of clerks who work in the bank's branches (clerk staff) and the status of the work of clerks who work in the Shoona or warehouses affiliated with the bank. The clerk's job level was higher than the employees in the Shoona.

The clerk works in an administrative office in one of the bank's branches, and does not work in the shop or warehouse (Shoona), while the employee works in the barn or

warehouse. The employee's grade is the first job grade in the employees' career hierarchy. The employee's salary is less than the clerk or scribe's salary. It is possible for a person to remain employed without being promoted until reaching the retirement age.

It was a requirement that any letter, whether official or personal, be signed in the name of the person who wrote the letter. It is an administrative order from the old that has been followed until the present time without any renewal.

Most of letter was written in English. Because the management of the bank is a English nationality and the bank is owned by the United Kingdom and this is clearly shown on the header of the letters. Barclays Bank (Dominion, colonial and overseas) (INCORPORATED IN UNITED KINGDOM WITH LIMITED LIABILITY).

The accuracy and splendor of the writing style of the Coptic clerks or scribe working in the bank, even though it is in English, indicates the competence of these clerks, and the level of good education that the Coptic clerks reached in that period. And their ability to adapt and change quickly with new events and circumstances

5.1.11. Administration and Payroll System:

At the end of 1829 to 1830, an administrative system for the work of employees, scribes and their assistants was established by Muhammad Ali Pasha, which was followed by all state Directorates and administration, and this led to indirectly affecting the administrative system of the state and the private sector during the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. The main jobs in the regions and their basic tasks were identified, like as at the present time a descriptive card was made for identified the tasks of each job in the state's administrative apparatus.¹

The system also established a specific salary limit so that the salary of any of these employees does not increase in any way. Determine the salaries of employees, scribes and their assistants as follows: -

Monthly salary	employment type
300 piasters	hand scribe
175 piasters	assistant hand clerk
200 piasters	report scribe
150 piasters	assistant report scribe

The salary of scribes was approved after that to prevent exceptions, and some jobs were abolished, others were created, and through the set of documents under study, we can know the amount or estimate of salaries that employees and scribes were getting at the beginning of the twentieth century. As it appears in Document No. 7 mentioned in its salary of Fahmy Mikhail was 14 pounds monthly and 683 piasters, with totally annual salary 176.196 in 1939. Another document No. was referred to salary of Fahmy Mikhail also with an increase amount it 5 pounds and that became his annual salary 190 pounds, while his monthly salary was 15.833.

As for document number 15 mentioned that salaries system at Barclays Bank was granting annual increase from the first of January per year. I think this system was applying in Ottoman Empire. It was granting its employees' salaries with annual amount divided on twelfth months.

5.1.12. Places and countries

5.1.12.1. Cairo

This city was established in 358 AH - 969 AD. On the evening of 17 Sha'ban 358 AH - 6 July 969 AD, the commander Jawhar arrived with soldiers of the Fatimid Caliph al-Muizz Lidin Allah in the city of Fustat. Jawhar moved to the place he chose to build Cairo and ordered the excavation of the foundation of the Caliph's Palace in it, and on the next

¹ Negm 1988: 108.

morning, which is the 18th of Sha'ban, he started building, and when Jawhar finished building the Caliph's Palace. He built a wall around it, that named his new city "Al Mansoura", after the name of Al-Mansur Abi Ismail, father Caliph Al-m'z Idīn al-lh abū tmīm m'd Al-Fatimi sire of Jawhar.¹

Jawhar also resided within the wall of Cairo the Al-Azhar Mosque, the soldiers' barracks, the residences of the courtiers, and the homes of the Moroccans who were helped the Caliph to the conquest of Egypt.

In the year 362 AH - 972 AD, the Caliph Al-m'z Idīn al-lh abū tmīm m'd, moved from the city of Mahdia, which was the capital of the caliphate in Tunisia in the west, to this city of Al-Mansuriyah (Cairo now), and he entered it on the 7th of Ramadan in the year 362 AH - 11 June in the year 973 AD. He stayed in the palace that Jawhar built for him, and from that date it was known as "Cairo" and Al-Mu'izz took it as the capital of the Fatimid caliphate.²

It is also called "Cairo of Al-Mu'izzieh" (al-qāhrī al-m'zī) and "qāhrī al-m'z" in reference to the Fatimid Caliph Al-Mu'izz (al-m'z), then it was known as "Misr"(Egypt) because its buildings have been overlapped with the city of Egypt (al-fstāt), which is known today as ancient Egypt. Now the name of "Misr" beats the name Cairo, given that the name of Egypt (Misr) is usually called on the largest city in the country. And was called also "Misr Al-Mahrousa" or "Al-Mahrousa" its mean "the guarded or protected", and this last name was, until recently, definite and specified in the Ministry of Defense to the administration of the Cairo or Misr "Al-Mahrousa sector", which was finally called "Cairo sector".

The oldest geographical book in which the name of Cairo was mentioned for the first time seven years after its establishment is Ibn Hawqal's book "Al-Masalik"³, as he mentioned it among the cities of Egypt with Fustat, al-Jazira, Giza, Qata'a (al-qtā'i'), Alexandria, Belbeis and Fayoum.⁴

The second book in which the name of Cairo is mentioned is the book "aḥsn al-tqāsīm" Its mean "Best of the apportionments" by al-Maqdisi, where he mentioned it seventeen years after its establishment, and said: Cairo is a city built by Jawhar al-Fatimi when he conquered Egypt. It is fortified with specific doors on the road to the Levant, and no one can enter the Fustat city except through it, because it is between the mountain and the river.

Al-Qazwini⁵ mentioned: "that it is a famous city near Fustat in Egypt, united by one wall, and it is today the great city, and it contains the King's House."

Amelineau⁶ also tells us: "that it is one of the important cities that was built in the tenth century AD, and it is the third fortified city established in Egypt after the city of Al-Qatay` and Al-Askar, and it was named "Kimi" an ancient Egyptian name, or it was named "Egypt" only, or "Cairo" in relation to the omnipotent star "Mars" that appeared in its sky when Gawhar started building the Cairo city".

Districts of Cairo governorate:

Azbakeya - Jamaliah - Al Khalifa - Al Darb Al Ahmar - Sayeda Zainab - Al Moski - Al Waili - Bab Al Shearia - Bulaq - Helwan Al Hammamat - Rod Al Farag - Shubra - Abdeen - Heliopolis - Old Cairo. ⁷

5.1.12.2. Minia:

The word "Minya" was written here in the documents in a different way from what is writing it now. Found in the document No. 1 it was written "Minya", while it is currently

¹ Ramzy (a) 1994: 3.

² Ramzy (a) 1994: 3.

³ Ibn Hawqal 1873: 97.

⁴ Ibn Hawqal 1992: 138.

⁵ Al-Qazwini 1980: 240.

⁶ Amelineau 2013: 380.

⁷ Ramzy (a) 1994: 4.

writing it "Minia", the letter "Y" has been replaced by the letter "I". It also wrote in the Arabic language with two different types, "منية" "mnī" and then it was changed to "منيا" "mnīā".

The origin of the word "Minia" or "Minya" as mentioned by Amelineau¹ in his geography: "Its Coptic name "Temoni" was also mentioned as "Tmoone". The word "Moone" means the nursing mother.² Goethe also mentioned in his dictionary that the old name of Minya is "Mnat khoufou", and he said that Katmir, Barkash and Amilino attributed it to "Minya", and Jomar attributed it to the place where the ruins of the city of "David"³ were located. Maspero achieved its location in the year (1891 AD) and put it exactly in a site of "Al-Anbaja", which was the center of the authority of the nobles of the middle empire in ancient Egypt, who were buried in Bani Hassan, located on the eastern bank (shore) of the Nile towards Abu Qurqas, and has nothing to do with the city of Minia the current.

Then Goethe mentioned in his dictionary that its Coptic name is "Tmoune", and scholars have confused between the word of "Moni" and word of "Tmoune". "Moni" means "the port",⁴ and it is the city of Minia, the down town of Minia the current, which was a port and a meeting place for trade convoys between the two seas and the river Nile. As for the word "Tmoune" which means "what Khufu nurtures" or "the nursing woman", which was used to refer to the estate (Properties) of Khufu's nurse, which he gave it to her in honor and in gratitude for her raising to him.⁵

It is currently located in "Zawiyat al-AMwat" or "Zawiyat Sultan", it is the city where the elite gathering (aristocracy) at that time. the aristocracy are the feudalism class which the people revolted on them after that, and this revolution was known as the Second Middle Age.

Until the 19th century, the city of Minia was a port and a gathering place for ships coming from the Upper and Lower Egypt areas in Egypt. The scientists of the French expedition left us with a wonderful painting of the port of the city of Minya,⁶ which extended, as shown in the picture, from the Church of Saint George and the El-Fouli Mosque⁷ to the "Al-Amrawi Mosque" or "Al-Wada Mosque" (Farewell), which is located opposite the current Nile Bridge.

At the same time, it was the wall and fortification of the city of Minia and its eastern entrances and gates, through it the customs or excise of goods were obtained.

The word "Minya" or "Minya" also means a fortress, along with the name of the aforementioned the port or the marina. The city of Minia had a strong fortress located directly on the bank of the river Nile that protected its people and guarded its Nile. And many regions in Egypt all have the same name "Minya" or "Minyat" attached to its name.⁸ Such as "Minyat Saqr" in "El Barsha",⁹ which is currently the region of the Monastery of Abba Bishoy in "Mallwy", and the monastery was in the past built as a fortress to protect monks, as well as "Minyat Tana", "Minyat Samanoud", and "Minyat Uqba", etc.¹⁰

¹ Amelineau 2013: 195.

² Ramzy (b) 1994: 196.

³The ruins of the City of David, according to the scientists of the French campaign, It is north of the ruins of Bani Hassan or Abu Qurqas, east of the Nile.

⁴ Al-Sharqawi 2010: 5.

⁵Samuel 2022: 12

⁶ Scientists of the French expedition 2005 plate No. 10.

⁷ For more El-Fouli Mosque: «El-Fouli Mosque»: <https://www.almasryalyoum.com/news/details/1395392>, accessed on 8/11/2023.

⁸ Amelineau 2013: 195.

⁹ al-Barmoussi 1992: 136. Samuel 2020: 139-140.

¹⁰ For more on these cities see: Amelineau 2013: 196-197.

It was also called the "Minya Bo Fess" or "Abba Fess"¹ starting from the fourth century AD. "Bo Fes" is disciple of Abba "Aba Hur",² which he built a monastery outside city of "Minia" during the 4 centuries. So "Minia" city become attributed (belong) to his name, in reference to the monastery of "Aba Feis" located west of the Nile outside the city of "Minya", which was inhabited by many monks who discipled on the hands of Saint "Aba Hur" and his disciple Abba Fess.³

Whatever, the current Minya is the old Minya that extends from the church of the great St. George and the "Al-Fouli" mosque in the north to the "Al-Wada" (Farewell) or "Al-Amrawi" mosque in the south, and from the west bank of the Nile (east) to Amir Al-Tajjar Street (between Al-Shawani currently) in the west, near the Military Police or the Ibrahimiya Canal, due to what this area contains of Pharaonic monuments, and Greco-Roman catacombs that indicate its ancient and historical roots.

In the Islamic era, during the Abbasid era, the region was known as "Miniyat Ibn al-Khasib," the most famous ruler of the Abbasid era, who ruled the El-Ashmounin region. Al-Khasib ibn Abd al-Hamid is the owner of the Kharag of Egypt by the Commander of the Faithful Harun al-Rashid,⁴ famous as Ibn al-Khasib. who sent him to the Minia region to humiliate its people, but he treated them in a good manner that involves love and appreciation, and the people of Minya lived in his time in prosperity and peace. So, Al-Ma'mun commanded to punish him, because he did not humiliate the people of Minya, and he did not obey him, and he sentenced him with poke (gouging) his eyes. But after that he regretted, so he gave him and his children El-Ashmunin territory.⁵

Yaqut al-Hamawi mentioned that Minya Abi al-Khasib: "A large, good city with many people and dwellings on the bank of the Nile in the middle Egypt, in It settled Abu alLamtti, one of the chiefs in those areas. And he established a beautiful mosque, and in its niche is the shrine of Abraham, peace be upon him."⁶

Ibn al-Jiaan mentioned: "that Muniyat Ibn al-Khasib follows the works of al-Ashmunin, and is divided into two districts, Makousah, i.e., "the current Maqusa". Which is the Kafr Minya of Bani Khasib. And it was in the name of Qatlubugha al-Kawkawi. And now it is property of the prince Yshabak Al-Dawadar. As for Minya of Bani Khasib and its kufr are outside Kafr Ma Koussa. And it was property of Prince Sargatmish Al-Ashrafy. And now it became subject to El Sharif Court (means Al sultan)".⁷

5.1.12.3. Dayrut

The city and center of Dayrout is the largest center in Assiut Governorate, as it contains a large number of villages that exceed 38 major villages. It was named by this name in relation to the largest and oldest of its villages, the village of Dayrut al-Sharif, which was known in the past as "Terot Sarabam", and then the Arabs wrote it to "Dayrout" which it means the dense tree or the nursing mother.

The Dayrout Center was established in the year 1826 AD, under the name of the Dayrout Department, and its headquarters was located in the town of Dayrout. And based on the

¹ The area of "Abba Fess" was mentioned in the Arab papyri as being within the "Kourat al-Ashmunin", which means that the name of this city remained in use during the Islamic era until the Abbasid era when Ibn al-Khasib assumed the mandate of the Ashmounin district. Abd el-Latif 2012: 142.

² Meinardus 2002: 182. Diocese of Minya and Abu Qurqas 1990: 15.

³ Samuel 2020: 195.

⁴ Al-Maqrizi 1987: 205.

⁵ Idris 1983: 33-39.

⁶ Yaqout al-Hamawi 1977: 218.

⁷ Ibn Al-Jiaan 1898: 182-183.

circular of the Ministry of the Interior, issued on December 3, 1889, the Dayrut Center was named, as of January 1, 1890, and it is still today.¹

5.1.12.4. Assiut

Assiut is a city established by the ancient Egyptians on the Nile River. During the Pharaonic era, it was called "Nomia", meaning the capital of the region. As for its general name at that time, Siut, which is derived from the word (Sawt or Siout), which means the guard in the ancient Egyptian language. It was in the era of the pharaohs a base for the region The thirteenth, and was inhabited by the Viceroy, and the Assiut region had a deity and a guard, an "Anubis" or "Ibn Awy", the guard of the royal tombs in the form of a dog, and it gained its importance in ancient Egypt because of its middle position among the regions of Pharaonic Egypt.²

Goethe stated: "Its old name is "Atf Khonti" and the civil name is "saout", which is composed of two syllables "si" it is meaning the guard, and "wat" it is meaning "way" or "road", which it is meaning "guardian of the road", as for the Assyrian name is "siya autu", and the Coptic name is "siout". During the Ptolemaic era of Egypt was called "Lycopolis" in Greek language: (Λυκόπολις), it is meaning "the city of the wolf", because its people worshiped "Ibn Awe" whom the Greeks likened to a wolf.³

In Mu'jam Al-Buldan, he mentioned that: "Assiut is a country in Upper Egypt, and in the letter Al-Sin is Siut, a city west of the Nile from the outskirts of Upper Egypt. It is a great city. Some Christians from its people told him that it had seventy-five churches for Christians and they were many. Famousest this churches monastery of Al Muharraq Assiut⁴. It was world, but he did not find better than Assiut. Koura⁵"assiut" continued to excel over other governorates until it became one of the parks of Abi Al-Juyoush Khamarwe.⁶

Ibn al-Wardi wrote on the Assiut and said: "As for Assiut, Akhmim and Dendera, they are eternal cities with amazing monuments and great elite...."⁷

Assiut is one of the oldest governorates in Egypt. And was a major center for trade caravans heading to the oases of the Western Desert, and the beginning of the path of Darb Al-Arbaeen, which reaches to Darfur city in Sudan. The city is distinguished as a meeting place for caravans coming from Sudan and Africa. It is a main point junction to receive African goods, so it has remained until this time an important commercial center and a destination for investors and business owners.⁸

5.1.12.5. Shoona

Shoona is a term known in the Mamluk era, which is the storehouse of the castle preserved in it the weapons and anything else. Shoona is a term is a term given to any place designated for storage. There was even a type of warship in the Ottoman era, which was designated for transporting the soldiers and equipment called "shoona".⁹

5.1.12.6. Barclays Bank

It was established on November 17, 1690 AD in London, England. It is one of the largest multinational banks in the world and the sixth oldest bank still in operation until now. The

¹ Ramzy (c) 1994: 9.

² Ramzy (c)1994: 7. Fakhry (WD):101. Bill 1973: 181-182. Al-Arini 1962: 85, 86.

³ Badawi & (eds) 2008: 38. Ramzy (c) 1994: 25.

⁴ Yaqut Al-Hamawi 1977: 170- 171.

⁵ Koura, means in Fatimid age a governorate in Arabic language.

⁶ Yaqut Al-Hamawi 1977: 193, 194.

⁷ Ibn al-Wardi 2001: 40.

⁸ Munis 1987: 393-396. Abdel Hamid 1996: 8.

⁹ Al-Khatib 1996: 278.

bank began as a banking company for the trade of gold and goldsmiths founded by "John Frim" and "Thomas Gold" in the year 1690 AD.¹

Beginning in 1736, James Barclay, Frem's son-in-law, became a partner in the bank. So, the bank was named Barclays after James Barclay.

At the end of the twentieth century, Barclays Bank began to expand its business by dominance other English banks, due to its large of transactions and its global presence.

Barclays Bank was established in Egypt in 1856 AD, 34 years before the National Bank, it established a branch in Alexandria and a branch in Cairo called Bank Misr, it is different about Bank Miser, which was established by Talaat Harb Pasha in 1920.²

In 1864 AD the name of the bank changed to "The Anglo-Egyptian Bank" with a paid-up capital of 500 thousand pounds sterling. In 1867 the name changed again to the "English-Egyptian Banking Company" and then returned to its first name in 1887 AD "The Anglo-Egyptian Bank". In 1925 AD it merged with another banks in Egypt, it was called "Barclays Bank (Dominion, Colonial, and overseas) incorporated in the United Kingdom with limited liability.

The first exodus from Egypt

On 1/14/1957 AD, Decree No. 22 was issued to Egyptianize banks, and became the foreign banks in Egypt subject to guardianship the government of Egypt. After that in 1961 were nationalized 149 companies by Law No. 11, seventeens banks were which it, including Barclays Bank. In 1975 AD, the British group returned to the market once again through a joint venture with "Bank of Cairo" under the name of "Cairo Barclays International".

In 1999, the British group raised its share to 60%, and in 2004 it raised its share to 100% to take over the entire company and changed the name to "Barclays Bank Egypt". It currently employs 1500 employees across 156 branches based in Cairo, Giza and Alexandria.

In 2014, "Barclays Bank Egypt" announced its desire to sell the bank in Egypt, and competed two banks to buy. They are "Emirates Bank Dubai" and "Commercial Wafa Moroccan Bank". In the end it sold to "Commercial Bank Wafa Morocco" with a value of 500 million Dollars.

VI. CONCLUSION

The category of Coptic clerks or scribes continued since the Arabs entered Egypt until the end of the twentieth century, as specialists and workers in financial and administrative affairs, warehouses, and land surveying, to the point that they passed these professions on to their children.

Barclays Bank documents showed the names of Coptic clerks who had a prominent position within Barclays Bank in Egypt, the most famous of whom was Fahmy Mikhail Effendi, who was a delegate for Barclays Bank in the city of Dayrout, Assiut Governorate. These documents also show the social status and cultural level that these Coptic clerks reached during that period from 1935 to 1955, that is, before World War II and after the Egyptian Revolution on July 27, 1952, both in terms of their mastery of the English language and dealing with it in official correspondence, or in terms of their proficiency in administrative systems and accounting transactions.

The study also revealed an important historical period in the social and economic history of Copts in Egypt during the twentieth century. Through it, we obtained very important and accurate information about the jobs of these clerks, their salaries, the annual increase in their salaries, the method of obtaining official vacations, the retirement referral system, the value of the retirement pension, the pension commutation system, its financial value, and the

¹ «History of Barclays Bank»: <https://home.barclays/who-we-are/our-history/>, accessed on 8/11/2023.

² Foxwell 1927: 411-417.

complaints and petitions system, which Fahmy Mikhail Effendi had presented some of them, to be transferred to Cairo, or to increase his salary, or to adjust the value of the pension commutation, and others.

The study also clarified the types of correspondence, and official letters in that period. I studied and examined the types of paper and the watermarks that appeared on it, through which I was able to identify the raw materials used in the paper industry, the names of the paper manufacturing companies, and the most famous brands, whether in operation until now, or Which was closed. We also found that the bank preferred to use paper with watermarks, especially in official and important correspondence, in order to make it easier to detect them in the case of forgery.

As well as the inks used in printing and writing, examination revealed that there were two types of these inks used in writing these documents: carbon ink, which was used in printing using printing machines, and iron ink, which was used in writing and signatures. Examination revealed that it was used in writing and signatures only due to its ability to fixed and penetrate in the tissue of the paper, in complete contrast to carbon ink, which requires use printing machines and other materials, to be the ink remain fixed on the paper.

Through this study, I was also able to trace the history of Barclays Bank in Egypt in that period, and to know its branches spread across Egypt, its foreign management system, the administrative hierarchy in the bank, the difference between the shoonah and the warehouse, the sub shoonah and the master shoonah, the payroll system, and the method of correspondence and communications that The most important of them was the broadcast receiver (wireless device), that got it every delegate of the bank in every branch of Barclays Bank in Egypt, by issuing an official license from the Egyptian government in the name the delegate of Barclays Bank.

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